

Systematisches und synonymisches Verzeichnis der Microlepidopteren Ungarns (Lepidoptera: Microlepidoptera)

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ABSTRACT: [Systematic and synonymic list of the Microlepidoptera of Hungary (Lepidoptera: Microlepidoptera)] – Checklist of the Hungarian Microlepidoptera fauna is presented after about 1896–2001 years. A systematic and synonymic list of 52 family and 2202 species of Microlepidoptera from the Hungary is given. *Catoptria persephone* Bleszynski, 1956 is currently a junior synonym of *Catoptria falsella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775).

Einleitung

Nach ABAFI-AIGNER et al. (1896) begann in der zweiten Hälfte des 18. Jahrhunderts die ungarische lepidopterologische Forschung : „Omnium, qui apud nos lepidopteris studuerunt, primus fuit A. J. SCOPOLI, professor academiae Semecziensis, qui in altera parte saeculi prioris, annis 1766–1776 studii causa lepidoptera colligebat, quem postea secuti J. MITTER-PACHNER et M. PILLER universitatis Budensis professores, qui suas in comitatu Pozsega animadversiones in opere „Iter per Poseganam Sclavoniae provinciam” inscripto anno 1783 juris publici fecerunt.”

Die erste Namensliste der ungarischen Kleinschmetterlinge wurde von PÁVEL & UHRYK (1896) angefertigt: ...”ex microlepidopteris species 1246 et variationes 26 enumeravimus”.

Die letzte vollständige Namensliste der ungarischen Microlepidoptera-Arten ist vor 34 Jahren erschienen (GOZMÁNY 1968). Die Systematik und Nomenklatur der Microlepidoptera hat sich in der letzten Zeit jedoch bedeutend geändert. Durch intensive faunistische Forschungen und taxonomische Revisionen wurde inzwischen die ungarische Fauna um viele neue Arten vermehrt. Bei einigen Taxa wurde festgestellt, dass diese nicht zur ungarischen Fauna gehören. Die 1996 erschienene Namensliste von KARSHOLT & RAZOWSKI ist hinsichtlich Ungarn nur teilweise genau. Bei vielen Taxa spiegelt sie die ungarischen Forschungen nicht wider und bedarf einer gründlichen Ergänzung.

In dieser Arbeit revidiere ich die aus Ungarn nachgewiesenen Arten vom Ende des 19. Jahrhundert bis heute. Die von mir als problematisch eingestufteten Arten werden in der Namensliste mit Fragezeichen und in eckigen Klammern: ? [*Platyptilia calodactyla* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)]. Ausführungen zu diesen mache ich am Ende der Arbeit bei den Anmerkungen. Ich strebe nicht an, eine komplette Liste aller Synonyme der einzelnen Arten anzugeben. Es werden nur diejenigen Synonyme genannt, die in der ungarischen Literatur regelmäßig erscheinen.

Da bei den Microlepidoptera bis heute keine einheitliche Systematik existiert, hat mir die Auswahl der systematischen Einteilung, die in der vorliegenden Liste Verwendung finden

sollte, besondere Schwierigkeiten bereitet. Ich habe mich mit einigen Änderungen (z.B. bei den Gelechiidae, Pterophoridae, Zygaenidae usw.) nach der Systematik von KARSHOLT & RAZOWSKI (1996) gerichtet. Dadurch ist es am ehesten möglich, den im Laufe der Zeit vorgenommenen Veränderungen zu folgen.

Die Literaturangaben am Ende der Arbeit sind das Ergebnis einer bewussten Auswahl. Als Grundwerk betrachte ich die bis jetzt erschienenen Microlepidoptera-Bände der „Fauna Hungariae“-Reihe (siehe GOZMÁNY & SZŐCS 1954–1977). Außer den schon erwähnten Publikationen habe ich nur die berücksichtigt, in der die Autoren neue Arten aus Ungarn mitteilten.

Jedem Forscher ist es bewusst, dass solch eine große Namensliste nie vollständig und ohne Fehler ist. Mein Ziel war lediglich, am Anfang des 3. Jahrtausends ein umfassendes Bild der ungarischen Microlepidopteren-Fauna zu geben, das auf eigenen Untersuchungen, erschienenen Publikationen und Sammlungsmaterial basiert.

An diesem Ort bedanke ich mich bei meinen Kollegen, die die Namenslisten der Familien kritisch durchgelesen und meine Arbeit mit nützlichem Rat unterstützt haben.

- Coleophoridae: G. BALDIZZONE (I – Asti)
- Pterophoridae: E. ARENBERGER (A – WIEN)
- Pyraloidea: W. SPEIDEL (D – Bonn)

Anmerkungen: Synonyme werden von mir nur dann angegeben, wenn diese in der ungarischen Literatur als gültige Namen vorkamen und für die Identifizierung der Taxa notwendig sind. Mehr als zwei Synonyme werden nur dann aufgezählt, wenn diese für das Verständnis der faunistischen Arbeiten nötig sind. Ein Beispiel ist *Stigmella aurella* (Fabricius, 1775) [Nepticulidae], deren Synonyme *nitens* Fologne, 1862, *fragariella* Heinemann, 1862 und *gei* Wocke, 1871 einige ungarische Forscher als eigenständige Arten behandelt hatten. Die Identifizierung der Taxa wurde oft dadurch erschwert, dass in dem als „Standard“ angenommenen ungarischen Microlepidoptera-Band (siehe Fauna Hungariae XVI. Band, Hefte 1–6) die Namen der Autoren oft falsch angegeben und das Beschreibungsdatum ganz vernachlässigt ist.

Bei mehreren Arten habe ich eine ergänzende Fußnote geschrieben, diese wurde mit einer hochgestellten Indexnummer nach dem Artnamen gekennzeichnet.

Aufgrund meiner früheren Untersuchungen (siehe FAZEKAS 1996: 27 p. und 1998a: 8–16 p.) habe ich vier Arten aus der ungarischen Fauna gelöscht. Ich habe festgestellt, dass die Arten [*Agriphila trabeatella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848; *Hellinsia pectodactyla* (Staudinger, 1859); *Zygaena contaminei* (Boisduval, 1834); *Zygaena diaphana* (Staudinger, 1887)] von ÁCS & SZABÓKY (1993) irrtümlich bestimmt wurden, sie sind also nicht Mitglieder der ungarischen Fauna. Belegexemplare konnten die Autoren nicht vorweisen.

Systematischer der Familie Überblick

- | | | |
|---------------------|-------------------|-----------------------|
| 01. Micropterigidae | 06. Heliozelidae | 11. Tineidae |
| 02. Eriocraniidae | 07. Adelidae | 12. Lypusidae |
| 03. Hepialidae | 08. Prodoxidae | 13. Psychidae |
| 04. Nepticulidae | 09. Incurvariidae | 14. Roeslerstammiidae |
| 05. Opostegidae | 10. Tischeriidae | 15. Douglasiidae |

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|----------------------|---------------------|-------------------------|
| 16. Bucculatricidae | 31. Scythrididae | 46. Zygaenidae |
| 17. Gracillariidae | 32. Chimbachidae | 47. Brachodidae |
| 18. Yponomeutidae | 33. Oecophoridae | 48. Sesiidae |
| 19. Ypsolophidae | 34. Lecithoceridae | 49. Cossidae |
| 20. Plutellidae | 35. Batracheridae | 50. Tortricidae |
| 21. Acrolepiidae | 36. Coleophoridae | 51. Choreutidae |
| 22. Glyphipterygidae | 37. Momphidae | 52. Urodidae |
| 23. Heliodinidae | 38. Blastobasidae | 53. Schreckensteiniidae |
| 24. Bedelliidae | 39. Pterolonchidae | 54. Epermeniidae |
| 25. Lyonetiidae | 40. Autostichidae | 55. Alucitidae |
| 26. Ethmiidae | 41. Amphibastidae | 56. Pterophoridae |
| 27. Depressariidae | 42. Cosmopterigidae | 57. Carposinidae |
| 28. Elachistidae | 43. Gelechiidae | 58. Thyrididae |
| 29. Agonoxenidae | 44. Limacodidae | 59. Pyralidae |
| 30. Deuterogoniidae | 45. Heterogynidae | |

Verzeichnis der bisher aus der Ungarn nachgewiesenen Microlepidoptera

LEPIDOPTERA HOMONEURA

MICROPTERIGOIDEA

01. MICROPTERIGIDAE

Micropterix Hübner, 1825

- M. aruncella* (Scopoli, 1763)
M. aureatella (Scopoli, 1763)
M. calthella (Linnaeus, 1761)
M. mansuetella Zeller, 1844
M. myrtetella Zeller, 1851
M. schaefferi Heath, 1975
M. tunbergella (Fabricius, 1787)

ERIOCRANIOIDEA

02. ERIOCRANIIDAE

Eriocrania Zeller, 1851

- E. subpurpurella* (Haworth, 1828)
fastuosella Zeller, 1839
E. sparrmannella (Bosc, 1791)
E. semipurpurella (Stephens, 1835)

HEPIALOIDAE

03. HEPIALIDAE

Triodia Hübner, 1820

- T. sylvina* (Linnaeus, 1761)
T. amasinus (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852)

Korscheltellus Börner, 1920

- K. lupulina* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Pharmacis Hübner, 1820

- Ph. fusconebulosa* (de Geer, 1778)
Ph. carna ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Phymatopus Wallengren, 1869

- Ph. hectus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Hepialus Fabricius, 1775

- H. humuli* (Linnaeus, 1758)

NEPTICULOIDEA

04. NEPTICULIDAE

Simplimorpha Scoble, 1983

- S. promissa* (Staudinger, 1871)

Stigmella Schrank, 1802

- S. naturnella* (Klimesch, 1936)
S. confusella (Wood & Walsingham, 1894)
S. freyella (Heyden, 1858)
S. tiliae (Frey, 1856)
S. betulicola (Stainton, 1856)
S. nivenburgensis (Preissecker, 1942)
S. sakhalinella PUPL, 1984
distinguenda auct.,
nec. Heinemann, 1872
S. luteella (Stainton, 1857)
S. glutinosae (Stainton, 1858)
rubescens Heinemann, 1871
S. elisabethella Szöcs, 1957
S. alnetella (Stainton, 1856)
S. microtheriella (Stainton, 1854)
S. prunetorum (Stainton, 1855)
S. aceris (Frey, 1857)
szöcsi (Klimesch, 1956)
S. malella (Stainton, 1854)
S. rhamnella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1860)
S. catharticella (Stainton, 1853)
S. anomalella (Goeze, 1783)
fletcheri Tutt, 1899
S. spinosissima (Watters, 1928)
S. centifoliella (Zeller, 1848)

- S. ulmivora* (Fologne, 1860)
 ulmifoliae Hering, 1931
 ulmicola Hering, 1932
S. ulmiphaga (Priessecker, 1942)
S. viscerella (Stainton, 1853)
S. sanguisorbae (Wocke, 1865)
S. thuringiaca (Petry, 1904)
S. rolandi van Nieukerken, 1990
S. paradoxa (Frey, 1858)
 nitidella Heinemann, 1862
S. torminalis (Wood, 1890)
S. regiella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. crataegella (Klimesch, 1936)
S. hahniella (Wörtz, 1890)
S. magdalenae (Klimesch, 1950)
S. nylandriella (Tengström, 1848)
S. oxyacanthella (Stainton, 1854)
 aeneella auct. nec Heinemann, 1862
S. pyri (Glitz, 1865)
S. minusculella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. desperatella (Frey, 1856)
 pyricola Wocke, 1877
S. hybnerella (Hübner, 1813)
 gratiosella Duponchel, 1843
 ignobilella Stainton, 1849
S. mespilicola (Frey, 1856)
 ariella Herrich-Schäffer, 1860
S. floslactella (Haworth, 1828)
S. carpinella (Heinemann, 1862)
S. tityrella (Stainton, 1854)
S. salicis (Stainton, 1854)
S. vimineticola (Frey, 1856)
S. benanderella (Wolff, 1955)
S. obliquella (Heinemann, 1862)
S. trimaculella (Haworth, 1828)
S. assimilella (Zeller, 1848)
S. plagiolella (Stainton, 1854)
S. lemniscella (Zeller, 1839)
 marginicolella Stainton, 1853
S. continuella (Stainton, 1856)
S. aurella (Fabricius, 1775)
 nitens Fologne, 1862
 fragariella Heinemann, 1862
 gei Wocke, 1871
S. splendidissimella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
 dulcella Heinemann, 1862
 ? [*S. aeneofasciella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)]^[1]
S. tormentillella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1860)
S. poterii (Stainton, 1857)
 geminella Frey, 1870
S. filipendulae (Wocke, 1871)
S. incognitella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
 pomella Vaughan, 1858
S. perpygmaeella (Doubleday, 1859)
 pygmaeella Hawort, 1828 nom. praecox.
- S. mali* M. hering, 1932
S. hemargyrella (Kollar, 1832)
S. speciosa (Frey, 1857)
 pseudoplatanella Weber, 1937
 lonicerarum (Frey, 1856)
S. basiguttella (Heinemann, 1862)
S. svenssoni (Johansson, 1971)
S. zangherii (Klimesch, 1951)
S. szoeciella (Borkowski, 1972)
S. dorsiguttella (Johansson, 1971)
S. ruficapitella (Haworth, 1828)
S. atricapitella (Haworth, 1828)
S. samiatella (Zeller, 1839)
S. roborella (Johansson, 1971)
S. eberhardi (Johansson, 1971)
***Acalyptris* Meyrick, 1921**
A. loranthella (Klimesch, 1937)
***Trifurcula* Zeller, 1848**
T. headleyella (Stainton, 1854)
T. thymi (Szöcs, 1965)
T. cryptella (Stainton, 1856)
T. eurema (Tutt, 1899)
 dorycniella Suire, 1928
T. ortneri (Klimesch, 1951)
T. pallidella (Duponchel, 1843)
T. chamaecytisi Z. & Lastůvka, 1994
T. aurella Rebel, 1933
T. beirneri Puplesis, 1984
***Parafomoria* van Nieukerken, 1983**
P. helianthemella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1860)
P. liguricella (Klimesch, 1946)
***Bohemannia* Stainton, 1859**
B. pulverosella (Stainton, 1849)
***Ectoedemia* Busck, 1907**
E. sericopeza (Zeller, 1839)
E. louisella (Sircom, 1849)
E. decentella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
E. septembrella (Stainton, 1849)
E. atrifrontella (Stainton, 1851)
E. liebwerdella (Zimmermann, 1940)
E. longicaudella Klimesch, 1953
E. intimella (Zeller, 1848)
E. hannoverella (Glitz, 1872)
E. turbidella (Zeller, 1848)
E. klimeschi (Skala, 1933)
E. argyropeza (Zeller, 1839)
E. priesseckeri (Klimesch, 1941)
E. caradjai (Groschke, 1944)
E. gilvipennella (Klimesch, 1946)
E. rufifrontella (Caradja, 1920)
 nigrosparsella Klimesch, 1940
E. gozmanyi (Szöcs, 1959)
E. albifasciella (Heinemann, 1871)
E. cerris (Zimmermann, 1944)
E. contorta van Niukernen, 1985

E. subbimaculella (Haworth, 1828)
E. heringi (Toll, 1934)
 quercifoliae Toll, 1934
 sativella Klimesch, 1936
E. liechtensteini (Zimmermann, 1944)
E. spiraeae Gregor & Povolny, 1983
E. agrimoniae (Frey, 1858)
E. hexapetalae (Szöcs, 1957)
E. angulifasciella (Stainton, 1849)
E. atricollis (Stainton, 1857)
 staphyleae Zimmermann, 1944
E. arcuatella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
E. rubivora (Wocke, 1860)
E. spinosella (Joannis, 1908)
E. mahalebella (Klimesch, 1936)
E. occultella (Linnaeus, 1767)
 mediofasciella (Haworth, 1828)
 argentipedella Zeller, 1839

05. OPOSTEGIDAE

***Opostega* Zeller, 1839**

O. salicella (Treitschke, 1933)
O. spatulella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
***Pseudopostega* Kozlov, 1985**
P. auritella (Hübner, 1813)
P. crepusculella (Zeller, 1839)

INCURVARIOIDEA

06. HELIOZELIDAE

***Antispila* Hübner, 1825**

A. metallella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 pfeifferella Hübner, 1813 nom.praeocc.
A. treitschkiella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1843)
***Heliozela* Herrich-Schäffer, 1853**
H. sericiella (Haworth, 1828)
 stanneella Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841
H. resplendella (Stainton, 1851)

07. ADELIDAE

ADELINAE

***Nemophora* Illiger & Hoffmannsegg, 1798**

N. deegerella (Linnaeus, 1758)
N. ochsenheimerella (Hübner, 1813)
N. raddella (Hübner, 1793)
N. metallica (Poda, 1761)
 scabiosella Scopoli, 1763
N. pfeifferella (Hübner, 1813)
N. cupriacella (Hübner, 1819)
N. violellus (Stainton, 1851)
N. auricella (Ragonot, 1874)
N. fasciella (Fabricius, 1775)
N. mollella (Hübner, 1813)
N. minimella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
N. dumerilellus (Duponchel, 1839)

***Adela* Latreille, 1796**

A. violella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. mazzolella (Hübner, 1801)
A. paludicolella (Zeller, 1850)
 orientella (Staudinger, 1870)
A. reaumurella (Linnaeus, 1758)
 viridella Scopoli, 1763
A. cuprella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. croesella (Scopoli, 1763)
A. reskovitsiella (Szent-Iványi, 1945)
***Cauchas* Zeller, 1839**
C. rufifrontella (Treitschke, 1833)
C. fibulella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. leucocerella (Scopoli, 1763)
C. uhrikmeszarosiella (Szent-Iványi, 1945)
C. rufimitrella (Scopoli, 1763)
 purpuratella Zeller, 1850

NEMATOPOGONINAE

***Nematopogon* Zeller, 1839**

N. pilella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1758)
N. schwarziellus Zeller, 1839
N. andansonella (Villers, 1789)
 panzerella (Fabricius, 1794)
N. metaxella (Hübner, 1813)
N. swammerdamella (Linnaeus, 1758)
N. robertella (Clerck, 1759)
 pilulella Hübner, 1813

08. PRODOXIDAE

***Lampronia* Stephens, 1829**

L. corticella (Linnaeus, 1758)
 rubiella (Bjerkander, 1781)
L. morosa Zeller, 1852
L. flavimitrella (Hübner, 1817)
L. rupella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
L. fuscataella (Tengström, 1848)
 tenuicornis Stainton, 1854
L. pubicornis (Haworth, 1828)

09. INCURVARIIDAE

***Incurvaria* Haworth, 1828**

I. pectinea Haworth, 1828
I. masculella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 muscalella Fabricius, 1787
I. oehlmanniella (Hübner, 1796)
I. praelatella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
I. koernerella (Zeller, 1839)
***Phylloporia* Heinemann, 1870**
Ph. bistrigella (Haworth, 1828)

TISCHERIOIDEA

10. TISCHERIIDAE

***Tischeria* Zeller, 1839**

T. ekebladella (Bjerkander, 1795)

T. dodonaea Stainton, 1858
T. decidua Wocke, 1876
Emmetia Leraut, 1993
E. marginea (Haworth, 1828)
E. szoecsi (Kasy, 1961)
E. heinemanni (Wocke, 1871)
E. gaunacella (Duponchel, 1843)
E. angusticollella (Duponchel, 1843)

TINEOIDEA

11. TINEIDAE

MYRMECOZELINAE

Ateliotum Zeller, 1839

A. hungaricellum Zeller, 1839

Hplotinea Diakonoff & Hinton, 1956

H. ditella (Pierce & Diakonoff, 1938)

H. insectella (Fabricius, 1794)

miscella Zeller, 1839

Myrmecozela Zeller, 1852

M. ochraceella (Tengström, 1848)

Cephimallota Bruand, 1851

C. angusticostella (Zeller, 1839)

simplicella Zeller, 1852

libanotica (G. Petersen, 1959)

Reisserita Agenjo, 1952

R. relicinella Zeller, 1839

MEESINAE

Matratinea Sziraki, 1990

M. rufilicaput Sziraki & Szöcs, 1990

Eudarcia Clemens, 1860

E. pagenstecherella Hübner, 1825

vinculella (Heidenreich, 1851)

Infurcitinea Spuler, 1910

I. roesslerella (Heyden, 1865)

I. albicomella (Stainton, 1851)

I. finalis (Gozmány, 1959)

I. argentimaculella (Stainton, 1849)

Stenoptinea Dietz, 1905

S. cyneimarmorella (Millière, 1854)

angustipennis Herrich-Schäffer, 1854

SCARDIINAE

Montescardia Amsel, 1952

M. tessulatellus (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

Scardia Treitschke, 1830

S. boletella (Fabricius, 1794)

polypori (Esper, 1804)

Morphaga Herrich-Schäffer, 1854

M. choragella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

boleti (Fabricius, 1776)

NEMAPOGONINAE

Triaxomera Zagulajev, 1959

T. fulvimitrella (Sodoffsky, 1830)

T. parasitella (Hübner, 1796)

Archinemapogon Zagulajev, 1859

A. yildizae Kocak, 1981

laterella Thunberg, 1794, nec Den. & Schiff. 1775

Nemaxera Zagulajev, 1964

N. betulinella (Paykull, 1785)

emortuella (Zeller, 1839)

Nemapogon Schrank, 1802

N. granella (Linnaeus, 1758)

N. cloacella (Haworth, 1828)

N. wolffiella Karlsholt & Nielsen, 1976

albipunctella Haworth, 1828

N. inconditella (Lucas, 1956)

heydeni Petersen, 1957

N. variatella (Clemens, 1859)

personella Pierce & Metcalfe, 1934

N. gravosaellus G. Petersen, 1957

N. hungaricus Gozmány, 1960

N. picarella Clerck, 1759

N. clematella (Fabricius, 1781)

arcella auct. nec (Fabricius, 1776)

N. nigralbella (Zeller, 1839)

N. falsistriella (Haas, 1881)

Triaxomasia Zagulajev, 1964

T. caprimulgella (Stainton, 1851)

Neurothausasia Le Marchand, 1934

N. ankerella (Mann, 1867)

TINEINAE

Trichophaga Ragonot, 1894

T. tapetzella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Elatobia Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

E. fuliginosella (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

Tineola Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

T. bisselliella (Hummel, 1823)

Tinea Linnaeus, 1758

T. pellionella Linnaeus, 1758

T. translucens Meyrick, 1917

metonella Pierce & Metcalfe, 1934

T. dubiella Stainton, 1859

turicensis Müller-Rutz, 1920

T. pallidella Stainton, 1851

T. nonimella (Zagulajev, 1955)

T. columbariella Wocke, 1877

T. semifulvella Haworth, 1828

T. trinotella Thunberg, 1794

Niditinea G. Petersen, 1957

N. fuscilla (Linnaeus, 1758)

fuscipunctella (Haworth, 1828)

N. striolella (Matsumura, 1931)

piercella (Bentinck, 1935)

Monopis Hübner, 1825

M. laevigella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

rusticella (Hübner, 1796)

M. weaverella (Scott, 1858)

M. obviella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
ferruginella Hübner, 1813 nec Thunberg, 1788
M. crocicapitella (Clemens, 1859)
M. imella (Hübner, 1813)
M. monachella (Hübner, 1796)
M. fenestratella (Heyden, 1863)

HIEROXESTINAE

***Oinophila* Stephens, 1848**

O. v-flava (Haworth, 1828)

EUPLOCAMINAE

***Euplocamus* Latreille, 1809**

E. anthracinalis (Scopoli, 1763)

TEICHOBIINAE

***Psychoides* Bruand, 1853**

P. verhuella Bruand, 1853
verhuellella (Stainton, 1854)

12. LYPUSIDAE

***Lypusa* Zeller, 1852**

L. maurella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

13. PSYCHIDAE

NARYCHINAE

***Diplodoma* Zeller, 1852**

D. laichartingella (Goeze, 1783)
herminata (Fourcroy, 1785)
marginepunctella (Stephens, 1829)
D. adpersella Heinemann, 1870
***Narycina* Stephens, 1836**
N. duplicella (Goeze, 1783)
monilifera (Fourcroy, 1785)
N. astrella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

Dahlicini

***Eosolenobia* Filipjev, 1924**

E. manni (Zeller, 1852)

***Praesolenobia* Sieder, 1954**

P. clathrella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837)

***Dahlica* Enderlein, 1912**

D. triquetrella (Hübner, 1813)
D. lichenella (Linnaeus, 1761)
norvegica (Strand, 1919)
D. inconspicua (Stainton, 1843)
D. nickerkii (Heinemann, 1870)

***Siederia* Meier, 1953**

S. pineti (Zeller, 1852)

***Postsolenobia* Meier, 1958**

P. thomanni (Rebel, 1936)
P. banatica (M. Hering, 1922)

TALEPORINAE

***Taleporia* Hübner, 1825**

T. politella (Ochsenheimer, 1816)
? ssp. szoecsi Sieder, 1955
T. tubulosa (Retzius, 1783)
? ssp. gozmanyi Sieder, 1955

TYPHONIINAE

Typhoniini

***Melasina* Boisduval, 1840**

M. ciliaris Ochsenheimer, 1810
lugubris Hübner, 1803, nec Fabricius, 1776

PSYCHINAE

Psychini

***Bacotia* Tutt, 1899**

B. claustralla (Bruand, 1845)

***Proutia* Tutt, 1899**

P. betulina (Zeller, 1839)
***Bruandia* Tutt, 1900**
B. comitella (Bruand, 1853)
***Psyche* Schrank, 1801**
P. casta (Pallas, 1767)
P. crassiorella (Bruand, 1851)

EPICHNOPTERIGINAE

Epichnopterigini

***Bijugis* Heylaerts, 1879**

B. bombycella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
B. pectinella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

***Rebelia* Heylaerts, 1900**

R. sapho (Millière, 1864)
? ssp. danubiella Loebel, 1941
R. kruegeri Turati, 1914
R. surientella (Bruand, 1858)
R. herrichiella Strand, 1912
plumella auct. nec (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

R. thomanni Rebel, 1937

R. hungarica Meier, 1957

Psychidea Rambur, 1866

P. nudella (Ochsenheimer, 1810)

***Acentra* Burrows, 1932**

A. vestalis (Staudinger, 1871)

A. subvestalis (Wehrli, 1933)

***Epichnopterix* Hübner, 1816**

E. plumella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
pulla (Esper, 1785)

E. kovacsi Sieder, 1955

***Whittleia* Tutt, 1900**

W. undulella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837)
W. paveli Uhryk, [? 1906]

OIKETICINAE

Acanthopsyche Heylaerts, 1881

- A. atra* (Linnaeus, 1767)
opacella Herrich-Schäffer, 1846
A. ecksteini (Lederer, 1855)
A. siederi Szöcs, 1961

Canephora Hübner, 1822

- C. hirsuta* (Poda, 1761)
unicolor (Hufnagel, 1766)

Pachythelia Westwood, 1848

- P. villosella* (Ochsenheimer, 1810)

Oreopsychni

Ptilocephala Rambur, 1866

- P. muscella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
P. plumifera (Ochsenheimer, 1810)

Phalacropterigini

Megalophanes Heylaerts, 1881

- M. viciella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Sterrhopterix Hübner, 1816

- S. fusca* (Haworth, 1809)
hirsutella Hübner, 1793
gozmanyi Kovács, 1953

Apterona Milliére, 1857

- A. helicoidella* (Vallot, 1827) (parth. form)
helix (Siebold, 1850)

GRACILLARIOIDEA

14. ROESLERSTAMMIIDAE

Roeslerstammia Zeller, 1839

- R. erxebella* (Fabricius, 1787)
erxebeniella Zeller, 1839
R. pronubella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

15. DOUGLASIIDAE

Tinagma Zeller, 1849

- T. perdicella* Zeller, 1839
T. ocnerosomella (Stainton, 1850)
T. balteolella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841)

Klimeschia Amsel, 1938

- K. transversella* (Zeller, 1839)

16. BUCCULATRICIDAE

Bucculatrix Zeller, 1839

- B. absinthii* Gartner, 1865
B. albedinella (Zeller, 1839)
B. artemisiella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
B. bechsteiniella (Bechstein & Scharfenberg, 1805)
crataegi Zeller, 1839
B. benacicolella Hartig, 1937
B. cantabricella Chrétien, 1898
B. cidarella (Zeller, 1839)
B. cristatella (Zeller, 1839)
B. demaryella (Duponchel, 1840)

- B. frangutella* (Goeze, 1783)

- B. gnaphaliella* (Treitschke, 1833)

- B. maritima* Stainton, 1851

- B. nigricomella* (Zeller, 1839)

- B. noltei* Petry, 1912

- B. ratisbonensis* Stainton, 1861

- B. rhamnella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855

- B. thoracella* (Thunberg, 1794)

- B. ulmella* Zeller, 1848

- B. ulmifoliae* M. Hering, 1931

17. GRACILLARIIDAE

GRACILLARIINAE

Parectopa Clemens, 1860

- P. ononidis* (Zeller, 1839)

- P. robiniella* Clemens, 1863

Micrurapteryx Spuler, 1910

- M. kollariella* (Zeller, 1839)

Caloptilia Hübner, 1825

- C. alchimiella* (Scopoli, 1763)

- C. cuculipennella* (Hübner, 1796)

- C. elongella* (Linnaeus, 1761)

- C. falconipennella* (Hübner, 1813)

- C. fidella* (Reutti, 1853)

- C. fribergensis* (Fritzsche, 1871)

- C. hauderi* (Rebel, 1906)

- C. hemidactylella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

- C. honoratella* (Rebel, 1914)

- C. rhodinella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)

- C. robustella* Jäck, 1972

- C. roscipennella* (Hübner, 1796)

- C. rufipennella* (Hübner, 1796)

- C. semifascia* (Haworth, 1828)

- C. stigmatella* (Fabricius, 1781)

Gracillaria Haworth, 1828

- G. loriollella* Frey, 1881

- G. syringella* (Fabricius, 1794)

Aspilapteryx Spuler, 1910

- A. limosella* (Duponchel, 1844)

- A. tringipennella* (Zeller, 1839)

Eucalybites Kumata, 1982

- E. auroguttella* (Stephens, 1835)

Calybites Hübner, 1822

- C. phasianipennella* (Hübner, 1813)

- C. quadrisignella* (Zeller, 1839)

Povolnya Kuznetsov, 1979

- P. leucapennella* (Stephens, 1835)

- sulphurella Haworth, 1828, nec Fabricius, 1176

Sauterina Kuznetsov, 1979

- S. hoffmanniella* (Schleich, 1867)

Acrocercops Wallengren, 1881

- A. brongniardella* (Fabricius, 1798)

Dialectica Walsingham, 1897

- D. imperialella* (Zeller, 1847)

- D. soffneri* Gregor & Povolny, 1965

Spulerina Vári, 1961*S. simploniella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1840)**Leucospilapteryx Spuler, 1910***L. omisella* (Stainton, 1848)**Ornixola Kuznetsov, 1979***O. caudulatella* (Zeller, 1839)**Callisto Stephens, 1834***C. denticulella* (Thunberg, 1794)**Parornix Spuler, 1910***P. anglicella* (Stainton, 1850)*P. anguliferella* (Zeller, 1847)*P. betulae* (Stainton, 1854)*P. carpinella* (Frey, 1863)*P. devoniella* (Stainton, 1850)

avellanella Stainton, 1854

P. favigora (Frey, 1861)*P. finitimella* (Zeller, 1850)*P. petiolella* (Frey, 1863)*P. scoticella* (Stainton, 1850)*P. szoecsi* (Gozmány, 1952)*P. tenella* (Rebel, 1919)*P. torquillella* (Zeller, 1850)**LITHOCOLLETINAE****Phyllonorycter Hübner, 1822***Ph. abrasella* (Duponchel, 1843)*Ph. acaciella* (Duponchel, 1843)*Ph. acerifoliella* (Zeller, 1839)

acernella Duponchel, 1843

Ph. agilella (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. alpina* (Frey, 1856)

hauderiella (Rebel, 1913)

Ph. apparella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)*Ph. blancardella* (Fabricius, 1781)*Ph. cavella* (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. cerasinella* (Reutti, 1852)*Ph. comparella* (Duponchel, 1843)*Ph. connexella* (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. coryli* (Nicelli, 1851)*Ph. corylifoliella* (Hübner, 1796)

betulae Zeller, 1839

Ph. cydoniella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*Ph. delitella* (Duponchel, 1844)*Ph. distentella* (Zeller, 1846)

manni Zeller, 1846

Ph. dubitella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)*Ph. emberizaepennella* (Bouché, 1834)*Ph. esperella* (Goeze, 1783)

quinnata Geoffroy, 1785

Ph. fraxinella (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. geniculella* (Ragonot, 1874)*Ph. froelichiella* (Zeller, 1839)*Ph. harrisella* (Linnaeus, 1761)

cramerella Fabricius, 1794

Ph. heegeriella (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. helianthemella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861)*Ph. hilarella* (Zetterstedt, 1839)

spinolella Duponchel, 1840

Ph. ilicifoliella (Duponchel, 1843)*Ph. insignetella* (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. kleemannella* (Fabricius, 1781)*Ph. lantanella* (Schrank, 1802)*Ph. lautella* (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. leucographella* (Zeller, 1850)*Ph. maestingella* (Müller, 1764)

faginella Zeller, 1846

Ph. mannii (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. medicaginella* (Gerasimov, 1930)*Ph. mespilella* (Hübner, 1805)

pomilifoliella Zeller, 1839

Ph. messaniella (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. muelleriella* (Zeller, 1839)*Ph. nicellii* (Stainton, 1851)*Ph. nigrescentella* (Logan, 1851)*Ph. oxyacanthae* (Frey, 1856)*Ph. parisiella* (Wocke, 1848)*Ph. pastorella* (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. phyllocytisi* (M. Hering, 1936)*Ph. persicella* Steudel, [? 1873]*Ph. platani* (Staudinger, 1870)*Ph. populifoliella* (Treitschke, 1833)*Ph. quercifoliella* (Zeller, 1839)*Ph. quinqueguttella* (Stainton, 1851)*Ph. rajella* (Linnaeus, 1758)*Ph. robiniella* (Clemens, 1859)*Ph. roboris* (Zeller, 1839)*Ph. sagitella* (Bjerkander, 1790)

tremulae Zeller, 1846

Ph. salicicolella (Sircom, 1848)*Ph. salictella* (Zeller, 1846)

viminiella Sircom, 1848

Ph. saportella (Duponchel, 1840)

hortella auctt. nec Fabricius, 1794

Ph. schrebella (Fabricius, 1781)*Ph. scitulella* (Duponchel, 1843)*Ph. sorbi* (Frey, 1855)*Ph. spinicolella* (Zeller, 1846)

cerasicolella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855

Ph. staintoniella (Nicelli, 1853)

desertella Gregor & Povolny, 1949

Ph. stettinensis (Nicelli, 1852)*Ph. strigulatella* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)*Ph. tenerella* (Joannis, 1915)

tenella (Zeller, 1846)

Ph. tristigella (Haworth, 1828)*Ph. ulmifoliella* (Hübner, 1817)**Cameraria Chapman, 1902***C. ohridella* Deschka & Dimič, 1986

PHYLLOCNISTINAE***Phyllocnistis* Zeller, 1848**

- Ph. labyrinthella* (Bjerkander, 1790)
Ph. saligna (Zeller, 1839)
Ph. unipunctella (Stephens, 1834)
 suffusella Zeller, 1847
Ph. xenia M. Hering, 1936

YPONOMEUTOIDEA**18. YPONOMEUTIDAE****SCYTHROPIINAE*****Scythropia* Hübner, 1825**

- S. crataegella* (Linnaeus, 1767)

YPONOMEUTINAE***Yponomeuta* Latreille, 1796**

- Y. evonymella* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Y. padella (Linnaeus, 1758)
 mahalebella Guenée, 1845
Y. malinella Zeller, 1838
Y. cagnagella (Hübner, 1813)
Y. rorrella (Hübner, 1796)
Y. irrorella (Hübner, 1796)
Y. plumbella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Y. sedella Treitschke, 1833
 vigintipunctata (Retzius, 1783)

***Euhypnometeuta* Toll, 1941**

- E. stannella* (Thunberg, 1794)

***Pseudoswammerdamia* Friese, 1960**

- P. combinella* (Hübner, 1786)

***Swammerdamia* Hübner, 1825**

- S. caesiella* (Hübner, 1796)
 heroldella Hübner, 1825
S. pyrella (Villers, 1789)
S. compunctella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
 nebulosella Stainton, 1870

***Paraswammerdamia* Friese, 1960**

- P. lutarea* (Haworth, 1828)

***Cedestis* Zeller, 1839**

- C. gysseleniella* Zeller, 1839
C. subfasciella (Stephens, 1834)
 farinatella Duponchel, 1840

***Niphonympha* Meyrick, 1914**

- N. albella* (Zeller, 1847)

PRAYDINAE***Atemelia* Herrich-Schäffer, 1853**

- A. torquatella* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

***Prays* Hübner, 1825**

- P. fraxinella* (Bjerkander, 1784)
 curtisella Donovan, 1793
P. ruficeps (Heinemann, 1854)
 rustica sensu auct., simplicella Herrich-Schäffer,
 1855

ARGYRESTHIINAE***Argyresthia* Hübner, 1825**

- A. laevigatella* (Heydenreich, 1851)
A. praecocella Zeller, 1839
A. arceuthina Zeller, 1839
A. dilectella Zeller, 1847
A. abdominalis Zeller, 1839
A. ivella (Haworth, 1828)
 andereggiella (Duponchel, 1838)
A. brockeella (Hübner, 1813)
A. goedartella (Linnaeus, 1758)
A. pygmaeella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 rudolphella (Esper, 1791)
A. sorbiella (Treitschke, 1833)
A. curvella (Linnaeus, 1761)
 arcella (Fabricius, 1776)
A. retinella Zeller, 1839
A. glaucinella Zeller, 1839
A. spinosella Stainton, 1849
 mendica auct., nec Hübner, 1796
A. conjugella Zeller, 1839
A. semifusca (Haworth, 1828)
 spiniella Zeller, 1839
A. pruniella (Clerck, 1759)
 pygmaeella sensu auct., nec (Denis & Schiff.,
 1775)
A. bonnetella (Linnaeus, 1758)
 nitidella (Fabricius, 1787)
A. albistria (Haworth, 1828)
A. semitestacella (Curtis, 1833)

19. YPSOLOPHIDAE**YPSOLOPHINAE*****Ypsolopha* Latreille, 1796**

- Y. mucronella* (Scopoli, 1763)
Y. dentella (Fabricius, 1775)
 xylostella auct., nec Linnaeus, 1758
Y. falcella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Y. asperella (Linnaeus, 1761)
Y. scabrella (Linnaeus, 1761)
Y. horridella (Treitschke, 1835)
Y. lucella (Fabricius, 1775)
Y. persicella (Fabricius, 1787)
Y. alpella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Y. sylvella (Linnaeus, 1767)
Y. parenthesesella (Linnaeus, 1761)
Y. ustella (Clerck, 1759)
 radiatella (Donovan, 1793)
Y. sequella (Clerck, 1759)
Y. vittella (Linnaeus, 1758)
Y. chazariella (Mann, 1866)

OCHSENHEIMERIINAE

Ochsenheimeria Hübner, 1825

- O. capella* Möscher, 1860
O. taurella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
mediopectinellus (Haworth, 1828)
birdella (Curtis, 1831)
O. urella Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1842
bisonella (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)
rupicaprella Möbius, 1935
O. vacuella Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1842
danilevskii Zagulajev, 1972

20. PLUTELLIDAE

Plutella Schrank, 1802

- P. xylostella* (Linnaeus, 1758)
maculipennis (Curtis, 1832)
P. porrectella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Rhigognostis Zeller, 1857

- R. incarnatella* (Stuedel, 1873)
R. kovacsi (Gozmány, 1952)
R. hufnagelii (Zeller, 1839)
Eidophasia Stephens, 1842
E. messingiella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1840)
E. syenitella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854

21. ACROLEPIIDAE

Digitivalva Gaedike, 1970

- D. valeriella* (Snellen, 1878)
D. arnicella (Heyden, 1863)
D. reticulella (Hübner, 1796)
cariosella (Treitschke, 1835)
D. pulicariae (Klimesch, 1956)
D. granitella (Treitschke, 1863)

Acrolepiopsis Gaedike, 1970

- A. assectella* (Zeller, 1839)
A. tauricella (Staudinger, 1871)
karolyii Szöcs, 1969

Acrolepia Curtis, 1838

- A. autumnitella* Curtis, 1838

22. GLYPHIPTERYGIDAE

ORTHOTELIINAE

Orthotelia Stephens, 1829

- O. sparganella* (Thunberg, 1788)

GLYPHIPTERYGINAE

Glyphipterix Hübner, 1825

- G. loricatella* (Treitschke, 1833)
G. thrasonella (Scopoli, 1763)
G. bergstraesserella (Fabricius, 1781)
G. equitella (Scopoli, 1763)
majorella Heinemann, 1876
minorella Snellen, 1882

- G. haworthana* (Stephens, 1834)

- G. forsterella* (Fabricius, 1781)

- lucasella Duponchel, 1840

- oculatella Zeller, 1850

- G. nattani* Gozmány, 1954

- G. pygmaeella* Rebel, 1896

23. HELIODINIDAE

Heliodines Stainton, 1854

- H. roesella* (Linnaeus, 1758)

24. BEDELLIIDAE

Bedellia Stainton, 1849

- B. ehikella* Szöcs, 1967

- B. somnulentella* (Zeller, 1847)

25. LYONETHIDAE

CEMIOSTOMINAE

Leucoptera Hübner, 1825

- L. lotella* (Stainton, 1859)
L. onobrychidella Klimesch, 1937
L. lustratella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
L. cytisiphagella Klimesch, 1938
L. laburnella (Stainton, 1851)
wailesella (Stainton, 1858)
L. spartifoliella (Hübner, 1813)
L. malifoliella (O. Costa, 1836)
scitella Zeller, 1839
L. heringilla Toll, 1938
L. aceris (Fuchs, 1903)
L. sinuella (Reutti, 1853)

LYONETHINAE

Lyonetia Hübner, 1825

- L. clerkella* (Linnaeus, 1758)
L. ledi Wocke, 1859
L. prunifoliella (Hübner, 1796)

GELECHIOIDEA

26. ETHMIIDAE

Ethmia Hübner, 1819

- E. dodecella* (Haworth, 1828)
decemguttella Hübner, 1810
E. quadrillella (Goeze, 1783)
inversella Fourcroy, 1785
funerella (Fabricius, 1787)
E. fumidella (Wocke, 1850)
E. candidella (Alphéraky, 1908)
E. pusiella (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. terminella T. Fletcher, 1938
E. bipunctella (Fabricius, 1775)
E. iranella Zerny, 1940
E. haemorrhoidella (Eversmann, 1844)

27. DEPRESSARIIDAE

Semioscopis Hübner, 1825

- S. avellanella* (Hübner, 1993)
S. oculella (Thunberg, 1794)
 anella (Hübner, 1796)
S. streikellneriana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
S. strigulana (Fabricius, 1787)

Luquetia Leraut, 1991

- L. lobella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Exaeretia Stainton, 1849

- E. preisseckeri* (Rebel, 1937)
 gozmányi (Balogh, 1951)
E. culcitella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)

Agonopterix Hübner, 1825

- A. ocellana* (Fabricius, 1775)
A. thapsiella (Zeller, 1847)
 feruliphila (Millière, 1866)
A. adspersella (Kollar, 1832)
A. assimilella (Treitschke, 1832)
A. nanatella (Stainton, 1849)
A. putridella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 peucedanella (Millière, 1881)
A. atomella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 pulverella (Hübner, 1825)
A. petasitis (Standfuss, 1851)
A. ciliella (Stainton, 1849)
A. arenella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. propinquella (Treitschke, 1835)
A. subpropinquella (Stainton, 1849)
 keltella (Amsel, 1935)
 amilcarella (Lucas, 1951)
A. laterella ([Denis & Schiffermülle], 1775)
 incarnatella (Zeller, 1854)
A. carduella (Hübner, 1817)
A. curpипunctosa (Haworth, 1811)
 zephyrella (Hübner, 1813)
A. yeatiana (Fabricius, 17819)
 ventosella (Stephens, 1834)
 oglatella (Chrétien, 1915)
A. alstroemeriana (Clerck, 1759)
A. purpurea (Haworth, 1811)
A. hereclina (Linnaeus, 1758)
 applana (Fabricius, 1776)
A. capreolella (Zeller, 1839)
A. rotundella (Douglas, 1846)
A. angelicella (Hübner, 1813)
A. astrantiae (Heinemann, 1870)
A. cnicella (Treitschke, 1832)
A. senecionis (Nickerl, 1864)
 cotoneastri (Nickerl, 1864)
 sarracenella (Rössler, 1866)
A. selini (Heinemann, 1870)
A. parilella (Treitschke, 1835)
A. oinochroa (Turati, 1879)
A. hippomathri (Nickerl, 1864)

- A. furvella* (Treitschke, 1832)
A. pallorella subpallorella (Staudinger, 1871)
A. kaekeritziana (Linnaeus, 1767)
 liturella (Denis & Schiff., 1775)
 flavella (Hübner, 1796)
A. liturosa (Haworth, 1811)
 liturella Hübner, 1796
 huebneri Bradley, 1966
A. nervosa (Haworth, 1811)
 costosa (Haworth, 1811)
A. daronicella (Wocke, 1849)

Horridopalpus Hannemann, 1953

- H. dictamnella* (Treitschke, 1835)

Depressaria Haworth, 1811

- D. pastinacella* (Duponchel, 1838)
 heracliana auct., nec Linnaeus, 1758
D. absynthiella Herrich-Schäffer, 1865
D. artemisiae Nickerl, 1864
D. marcella Rebel, 1901
 cuprinella Walsingham, 1907
 chneouriella Lucas, 1939
D. depressana (Fabricius, 1775)
 depressella Fabricius, 1798
D. chaerophyllii Zeller, 1839
D. ultimella Stainton, 1849
D. pimpinellae Zeller, 1839
 reichlini Heinemann, 1870
D. badiella (Hübner, 17969)
 brunneella Ragonot, 1874
 frustratella Rebel, 1936
D. corticinella Zeller, 1854
 uhrykella Fuchs, 1903
D. libanotidella Schläger, 1849
D. pulcherrimella Stainton, 1849
 semenovi Krulikowski, 1903
D. douglasella Stainton, 1849
D. emeritella Stainton, 1849
D. albipunctella (Denis & Schiff., 1775)
 aegopodiella (Hübner, 1825)
D. olerella Zeller, 1854
D. cervicella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854

28. ELACHISTIDAE

Cosmiotes Clemens, 1860

- C. freyerella* (Hübner, 1825)
C. stabilella (Stainton, 1858)

Mendesia Joannis, 1902

- M. farinella* (Thunberg, 1794)
M. huemeri Traugott-Olsen, 1990

Perittia Stainton, 1854

- P. herrichiella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)

Stephensia Stainton, 1858

- S. brunnichiella* (Linnaeus, 1767)

***Elachista* Treitschke, 1833**

- E. adscitella* Stainton, 1851
revinctella auctt., nec Zeller, 1850
- E. albidella* Nylander, 1848
- E. alpinella* Stainton, 1854
monticola Wocke, 1876
- E. anserinella* Zeller, 1839
- E. apicipunctella* Stainton, 1849
- E. argentella* (Clerck, 1759)
- E. atricomella* Stainton, 1849
holdenella Stainton, 1854
- E. bedelrella* (Sircom, 1848)
nigrella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
lugdunensis Frey, 1859
- E. biatomella* (Stainton, 1848)
- E. bisulcella* (Duponchel, 1843)
zonariella Tengström, 1848
- E. canapennella* (Hübner, 1813)
pulchella Haworth, 1828
incanella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
- E. chrysodesmella* Zeller, 1850
- E. cingillella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
- E. collitella* (Duponchel, 1843)
- E. contaminatella* Zeller, 1847
- E. dimicatella* Rebel, 1903
- E. disemiella* Zeller, 1847
- E. dispilella* Zeller, 1839
- E. dispunctella* (Duponchel, 1843)
- E. elegans* Frey, 1859
- E. gangabella* Zeller, 1850
taeniatella Stainton, 1857
- E. gleichenella* (Fabricius, 1781)
- E. griseella* (Duponchel, 1843)
dispositella Frey, 1859
- E. hedemanni* Rebel, 1899
- E. heringi* Rebel, 1899
- E. herrichii* Frey, 1859
reuttiana Frey, 1859
- E. humilis* Zeller, 1850
perplexella Stainton, 1859
- E. juliensis* Frey, 1870
- E. kilmunella* Stainton, 1849
stagnalis Frey, 1859
- E. klimeschi* Parenti, 1981
- E. luticomella* Zeller, 1839
flavicomella Stainton, 1856
- E. manni* Traugott-Olsen, 1992
- E. martinii* O. Hofmann, 1898
- E. megerella* (Hübner, 1810)
- E. monosemiella* Rössler, 1881
cerrusella Hübner, 1796 nom. praeocc.
- E. nitidulella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
- E. poae* Stainton, 1855
- E. pollinariella* Zeller, 1839
- E. pollutella* Duponchel, 1843

- E. pomerana* Frey, 1870
- E. pullicomella* Zeller, 1839
- E. quadripunctella* (Hübner, 1825)
quadrella sensu Hübner, 1805
- E. revinctella* Zeller, 1850
- E. rudectella* Stainton, 1851
- E. rufocinerea* (Haworth, 1828)
- E. scirpi* Stainton, 1887
- E. serricornis* Stainton, 1854
- E. spumella* Caradja, 1920
- E. squamosella* (Duponchel, 1843)
- E. subalbidella* Schläger, 1847
- E. subnigrella* Douglas, 1853
- E. subocellea* (Stephens, 1834)
disertella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
- E. szocsi* Parenti, 1978
- E. triatomea* (Haworth, 1828)
- E. triseriatella* Stainton, 1854
- E. unifasciella* (Haworth, 1828)
- E. utonella* Frey, 1856
paludum Frey, 1859

***Dibrachia* Sinev & Sruoga, 1992**

- D. kalki* Parenti, 1978

29. AGONOXENIDAE***Chrysoclista* Stainton, 1854**

- Ch. linneella* (Clerck, 1759)
- Ch. lathamella* T. Fletcher, 1936
bimaculella Haworth, 1828

***Heinemannia* Wocke, 1876**

- H. laspeyrella* (Hübner, 1796)
- H. festivella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

***Blastodacna* Wocke, 1876**

- B. atra* (Haworth, 1828)
putripennella Zeller, 1839
- B. hellerella* (Duponchel, 1838)

***Spuleria* O. Hofmann, 1897**

- S. flavicaput* (Haworth, 1828)
aurifrontella Geyer, 1832

***Dystebenna* Spuler, 1910**

- D. stephensi* (Stainton, 1849)

***Tetanocentria* Rebel, 1902**

- T. albanica* Rebel & Zerny, 1932
- T. ochraceella* Rebel, 1903

30. DEUTEROGONIIDAE***Deuteronomia* Rebel, 1901**

- D. pudorina* (Wocke, 1857)

31. SCYTHRIDIDAE***Scythis* Hübner, 1825**

- S. obscurella* (Scopoli, 1763)
- S. cuspidella* (Denis & Schiff., 1775)
- S. bengtssoni* Patočka & Liska, 1989
- S. productella* (Zeller, 1839)

S. seliniella (Zeller, 1839)
S. subseliniella (Heinemann, 1876)
S. fallacella (Schläger, 1847)
S. tabidella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. aerariella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. flaviventrella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. fuscoaenea (Haworth, 1828)
S. gozmanyi Passserin d'Entrèves, 1986
S. picaepennis (Haworth, 1828)
S. crassiuscula (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. bifissella (O. Hofmann, 1889)
S. pascuella (Zeller, 1855)
S. hungaricella Rebel, 1917
S. tributella (Zeller, 1847)
terrenella (Zeller, 1847)
parvella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. paulella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)
S. palustris (Zeller, 1855)
S. laminella (Denis & Schiff., 1775)
S. emichi (Anker, 1870)
S. vittella (O. Costa, 1834)
restigerella (Zeller, 1839)
S. limbella (Fabricius, 1775)
S. siccella (Zeller, 1839)
S. podoliensis Rebel, 1938
***Parascythris* Hannemann, 1960**
P. muelleri (Mann, 1871)

32. CHIMABACHIDAE

***Diurnea* Haworth, 1811**

D. fagella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
D. lipsiella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
phryganella Hübner, 1796

***Dasytroma* Curtis, 1833**

D. salicella (Hübner, 1796)

33. OECOPHORIDAE

OECOPHORINAE

Oecophorini

***Bisigna* Toll, 1956**

B. procerella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

***Fabiola* Busck, 1908**

F. pokorny (Nickerl, 1864)

***Schiffermuelleria* Hübner, 1825**

Sch. schaefferella (Linnaeus, 1758)

***Schiffremuellerina* Leraut, 1989**

Sch. grandis (Desvignes, 1842)

***Buvatina* Leraut, 1984**

B. stroemella (Fabricius, 1779)

***Denisia* Hübner, 1825**

D. luctuosella (Duponchel, 1840)

D. augustella (Hübner, 1796)

D. similella (Hübner, 1796)

D. stipella (Linnaeus, 1758)

***Decantha* Busck, 1908**

D. borkhauseni (Zeller, 1839)

***Metalampra* Toll, 1956**

M. cinnamomea (Zeller, 1839)

M. diminutella (Rebel, 1931)

***Endrosis* Hübner, 1825**

E. sarcitrella (Linnaeus, 1758)

lactella (Denis & Schiff., 1775)

lacteella (lapsus calami)

***Hofmannophila* Spuler, 1910**

H. pseudospretella (Stainton, 1849)

***Borkhausenia* Hübner, 1825**

B. minutella (Linnaeus, 1758)

B. fuscens (Haworth, 1828)

***Crassa* Bruand, 1850**

C. tinctella (Hübner, 1796)

C. unitella (Hübner, 1796)

***Batia* Stephens, 1834**

B. lambdella (Donovan, 1793)

magnatella Jäckh, 1942

B. internella Jäckh, 1972

B. lunaris (Haworth, 1828)

***Epicallima* Dyar, 1903**

E. bruandella (Ragonot, 1889)

E. formosella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

***Esperia* Hübner, 1825**

E. krueperella (Staudinger, 1871)

E. oliviella (Fabricius, 1794)

***Oecophora* Latreille, 1796**

O. bractella (Linnaeus, 1758)

***Alabonia* Hübner, 1825**

A. staintoniella (Zeller, 1850)

***Harpella* Schrank, 1802**

H. forficella (Scopoli, 1763)

***Carcina* Hübner, 1825**

C. quercana (Fabricius, 1775)

Pleurotini

***Minetia* Leraut, 1991**

M. crinitus (Fabricius, 1798)

M. adamczewskii Toll, 1956

M. labiosella (Hübner, 1810)

M. criella (Treitschke, 1835)

***Pleurota* Hübner, 1825**

P. marginella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

rostrella Hübner, 1796

P. pyropella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

P. bicostella (Clerck, 1759)

P. brevispinella (Zeller, 1847)

P. pungitiella Herrich-Schäffer, 1852

P. aristella (Linnaeus, 1767)

***Holoscolia* Zeller, 1839**

H. huebneri Kocak, 1980

Orophiiini

Cephalispheira Bruand, 1850

- C. denisella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. ferrugella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. sordidella (Hübner, 1796)
C. sareptensis Möschler, 1862

Telechrysidini

Telechrysis Toll, 1956

- T. tripuncta* (Haworth, 1828)

STATHMOPODINAE

Stathmopoda Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- S. pedella* (Linnaeus, 1761)

34. LECITHOCERIDAE

LECITHOCERINAE

Homaloxestis Meyrick, 1910

- H. briantiella* (Turati, 1879)

Lecithocera Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- L. nigrana* (Duponchel, 1836)
 luticornella Zeller, 1839

Odites Walsingham, 1891

- O. kollarella* (O. Costa, 1832)

35. BATRACHERIDAE

Batrachedra Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- B. praeangusta* (Haworth, 1828)
B. pinicolella (Zeller, 1839)

36. COLEOPHORIDAE

Augasma Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- A. aeratella* (Zeller, 1839)

Metriotes Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- M. lutarea* (Haworth, 1828)
 modestella Duponchel, 1838
 splendidella Lienig & Zeller, 1846

Goniodoma Zeller, 1849

- G. auroguttella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841)

Coleophora Hübner, 1822

- C. albella* (Thunberg, 1788)
 leucapennella Hübner, 1867
 albifuscella Zeller, 1839
C. spiraeella Rebel, 1916
C. lutipennella (Zeller, 1838)
C. longicornella Constant, 1893
C. ochripennella Zeller, 1849
C. gryphipennella (Hübner, [1796])
 obscura Haworth, 1828
 mariniella Hodgkinson, 1881
 scolopiphora O. Hering, 1926
C. flavipennella (Duponchel, 1843)
C. milvipennis Zeller, 1839
C. badiipennella (Duponchel, 1843)
C. limosipennella (Duponchel, 1843)
C. siccifolia Stainton, 1856

- betulifolia* Stainton, 1858

- C. kroenella* Fuchs, 1899
C. coracipennella (Hübner, 1796)
C. serratella (Linnaeus, 1761)
 fuscedinella Zeller, 1849
 metallicella Hodgkinson, 1892
 aetiopiformis Strand, 1902
C. prunifoliae Doets, 1944
 pseudoprunifoliae Capuse, 1971
C. hydrolapathella M. Hering, 1924
C. cecidophorella Oudejans, 1972
C. trigeminella Fuchs, 1881
C. cornutella Herrich-Schäffer, 1861
 cornuta Heinemann & Wocke, 1876
C. fuscocuprella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
C. lusciniapennella (Treitschke, 1833)
 viminetella Zeller, 1849
C. violacea (Ström, 1783)
 paripennella auct., nec Zeller, 1839
 hornigi Toll, 1952
 albicornuella Bradley, 1956
C. juncicolella Stainton, 1851
 infantilella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
 infantinella Frey, 1856
C. orbitella Zeller, 1849
 wilkinsoni Scott, 1861
C. binderella (Kollar, 1832)
 lusciniapennella Zeller, 1839
 politella Scott, 1861
 bicorella Stainton, 1861
C. ahenella Heinemann, 1876
C. albitarsella Zeller, 1849
C. pulmonariella Ragonot, 1874
C. trifolii (Curtis, 1832)
 frischella auct., nec Linnaeus, 1758
 chalybaella Costa, 1836
 melilotella Scott, 1861
C. frischella (Linnaeus, 1758)
 dannehli Toll, 1952
 auronitella Toll, 1962
C. alcyonipennella (Kollar, 1832)
 cuprariella Zeller, 1847
C. conyzae Zeller, 1868
C. ptarmicia Walsingham, 1910
C. striolatella Zeller, 1849
C. obviella Rebel, 1914
C. uralensis Toll, 1961
C. lineolea (Haworth, 1828)
 crocogrammos Zeller, 1849
 balloticoella Bruand, 1851
C. niveiciliella O. Hofmann, 1877
 edithae Gozmány, 1951
C. hemerobiella (Scopoli, 1763)
 anseripennella Hübner, [1810–13]
C. klimeschiella Toll, 1952

- C. eurasiatica* Baldizzone, 1989
C. lithargyrinella Zeller, 1849
 solitariella Zeller, 1849
 olivaceella Stainton, 1854
 annulipes Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
 fuscataella Toll, 1952
 fuscocuprella Toll, 1952
C. onobrychiella Zeller, 1849
 arenariella Zeller, 1865
C. medelichensis Krone, 1908
C. colutella (Fabricius, 1794)
 crocinaella Tengström, 1848
 serenella Duponchel, 1843
C. trifariella Zeller, 1849
C. genistae Stainton, 1857
C. saturatella Stainton, 1850
 tinctoriella Coverdale, 1885
C. niveocostella Zeller, 1839
 longicostella Stainton, 1867
C. albicostella (Duponchel, 1842)
 marginatella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
 approximatella Gozmány, 1956
C. discordella Zeller, 1849
 dorycniella Hartig, 1938
C. acrisella Millière, 1872
C. bilineatella Zeller, 1849
 perserenella Rebel, 1919
 joannisella Suire, 1930
 sergii Gozmány, 1956
 depauperella Toll, 1962
C. fringillella Zeller, 1839
C. vulpecula Zeller, 1849
C. congeriella Staudinger, 1859
C. chalcogrammella Zeller, 1839
C. deauratella Lienig & Zeller, 1846
C. mayrella (Hübner, 1813)
 spissicornis Haworth, 1828
 trochilipennella Costa, [1836]
 tuscaemiliella Constantini, 1923
C. hieronella Zeller, 1849
C. ballotella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
C. anatipennella (Hübner, 1796)
 bernoulliella Goeze, (1783)
 tiliella Zeller, 1849
C. albidella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 termbleyana Villers, 1789
 ? incanella Tengström, 1848
C. kuehnella (Goeze, 1783)
 lamellifera Geoffroy, 1785
 lamellatella Villers, 1789
 palliatella Zincken, 1813
 pallipennella Treitschke, 1833
 enervatella Zellr, 1849
 auricigrandella Bruand, [1851]
C. ibipennella Zeller, 1849
 nemorum Heinemann, 1854
 ardeapennella Scott, 1860
 alba Toll, 1952
 peralba Toll, 1953
 quercivorella Capuse, 1971
C. betulella Heinemann, 1876
C. zelleriella Heinemann, 1854
 pannonicella Gozmány, 1956
 platyphyllae Oku, 1965
C. currucipennella Zeller, 1839
 nemorum Heinemann, 1854
 tristrigella Heinemann & Wocke, 1877
 alaudipennella Capuse, 1971
 cristinae Capuse, 1971
C. brevipennella Wocke, 1874
C. serratulella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
C. virgatella Zeller, 1849
C. chamaedriella Bruand, 1852
C. serpylletorum E. Hering, 1889
C. auricella (Fabricius, 1794)
 paucinotella Toll, 1961
C. gallipennella (Hübner, 1796)
C. stramentella Zeller, 1849
C. kasyi Toll, 1961
C. coronillae Zeller, 1849
 constantella Bruand, 1858
C. flaviella Mann, 1857
C. vibicigerella Zeller, 1839
 mandschuriae Toll, 1942
 didyma Toll, 1957
C. conspicuella Zeller, 1849
 similis Staudinger, 1880
C. partitella Zeller, 1849
C. ditella Zeller, 1849
 roessleri Heinemann & Wocke, 1877
 anatolica Toll, 1952
C. fuscociliella Zeller, 1849
 medaciginis Herrich-Schäffer, 1861
C. pseudoditella Baldizzone & Patzak, 1983
 ditella Zeller, 1849 partim
C. astragalella Zeller, 1849
C. sumptuosella Toll, 1952
C. cracella Vallot, 1835
 lugduniella Stainton, 1859
C. caelebipennella Zeller, 1839
C. vibicella (Hübner, [1813])
 vibicipennella Treitschke, 1833
 brunneella Müller-Rutz, 1922
C. vicinella Zeller, 1849
C. ochrea (Haworth, 1828)
 argentipennella Duponchel, 1838
 hapsella Zeller, 1839
 castelensis Rebel, 1919
 quadrilineolla Turati, 1932
 argentivittella Toll, 1952

- digrammella Toll, 1953
- C. bilineella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
- C. livella* Zeller, 1849
- C. ornatipennella* (Hübner, [1796])
ornatea Haworth, 1828
- C. oriolella* Zeller, 1849
siliquella Constant, 1893
mongetella Chrétien, 1900
hafneri Prohaska, 1926
- C. vulnerariae* Zeller, 1839
icterella Duponchel, 1840
- C. glaseri* Toll, 1961
- C. hospitella* Chrétien, 1915
eupepla Gozmány, 1954
- C. pennella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
borowskiella Goeze, 1783
mucosa Geoffroy, 1785
muscosella Villers, 1789
onosmella Brahm, 1791
struthionipennella Treitschke, 1833
hispanicella Möchler, 1866
diffinis Staudinger, 1880
nervosella Müller-Rutz, 1927
flavilineella Toll, 1952
gogovi Capuse, 1971
- C. laricella* (Hübner, [1814–17])
laricinella Ratzenburg, 1840
nigricornis Heinemann & Wocke, 1877
- C. antennariella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1861
- C. adjunctella* Hodgkinson, 1882
paludicola Stainton, 1886
aratorensis Barasch, 1934
- C. caespitiella* Zeller, 1839
lacunaecolella Duponchel, 1833
- C. tamesis* Waters, 1929
- C. glaucicolella* Wood, 1892
- C. otidipennella* (Hübner, 1817)
murinipennella Duponchel, 1844
- C. alticolella* Zeller, 1849
- C. taeniipennella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
- C. salinella* Stainton, 1858
- C. sylvaticella* Wood, 1892
etelka Gozmány, 1954
- C. obscennella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
virgaureae Stainton, 1857
- C. halophilella* Zimmermann, 1926
- C. magyarica* Baldizzone, 1983
- C. therinella* Tengström, 1848
- C. pratella* Zeller, 1871
- C. linosyris* M. Hering, 1937
- C. asteris* Mühlig, 1864
- C. saxicolella* (Duponchel, 1843)
flavaginella auct., nec Lienig & Zeller, 1846
annulatella Tengström, [1848]
benanderi Kanerva, 1941
- C. narbonensis* Baldizzone, 1990
- C. pseudolinosyris* Kasy, 1979
- C. motacillella* Zeller, 1849
palumbipennella Toll, 1952
székessyi Gozmány, 1956
- C. sternipennella* (Zetterstedt, 1839)
punctipennella Tengström, [1849]
muehligiella Stainton, 1887
moenicella Stainton, 1887
- C. nomgona* Falkovitsh, 1975
- C. squamosella* Stainton, 1856
erigerella Ford, 1935
podolensis Toll, 1938
sabulicola Benander, 1939
- C. versurella* Zeller, 1849
miserella Staudinger, 1880
agricolella Fuchs, 1886
atlanticella Rebel, 1896
constanti Hering, 1942
klimeschi Vlach, 1942
saccharella Amsel, 1953
- C. corsicella* Walsingham, 1898
- C. dentiferella* Toll, 1952
- C. vestianella* (Linnaeus, 1758)
laripennella Zetterstedt, 1839
tengstromella Doubleday, 1859
subtractella Caradja, 1920
botauripennella Toll, 1955
- C. atriplicis* Meyrick, 1828
- C. absinthii* Wocke, 1876
- C. artemisicolella* Bruand, 1855
- C. punctulatella* Zeller, 1849
camphorosmella Constant, 1885
- C. remizella* Baldizzone, 1983
- C. chrysanthemii* O. Hofmann, 1869
- C. odorariella* Mühlig, 1857
- C. gnaphalii* Zeller, 1839
gnaphaliella Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
- C. riffelensis* Rebel, 1913
klemensiewiczzi Toll, 1950
fischeri Toll, 1950
eudoriella Toll, 1952
eudoriella Toll, 1952
- C. dianthivora* Walsingham, 1901
- C. galbulipennella* Zeller, 1838
otitae Zeller, 1939
- C. galatellae* M. Hering, 1942
- C. millefolii* Zeller, 1849
- C. peribenanderi* Toll, 1943
benanderi Toll, 1942
- C. thymi* M. Hering, 1942
- C. amellivora* Baldizzone, 1979
lineariella Zeller auct.
calcariella Chrétien auct.
- C. ramosella* Zeller, 1849

vlachi Toll, 1953
 albicornis Benander, 1936
 C. *trochilella* (Duponchel, 1843)
 troglodytella auctt., nec Duponchel, 1843
 lineatella Tengström, [1848]
 alpicola Heinemann & Wocke, 1877
 corymbosella Bauer, 1917
 axana Herinf, 1942
 C. *frankii* A. Schmidt, 1887
 C. *linosyridella* Fuchs, 1880
 C. *directella* Zeller, 1849
 scolopacipennella Wallengren, 1859
 scolopacinella Staudinger & Rebel, 1901
 C. *inulae* Wocke, 1876
 C. *striatipennella* Nylander, in Tengström, [1848]
 alpicella Stainton, 1858
 cacuminatella Doubleday, 1859
 C. *solitariella* Zeller, 1849
 C. *tanacetii* Mühlhig, 1865
 pallida Toll, 1942
 C. *artemisiella* Scott, 1861
 simillimella Fuchs, 1881
 digitella Palm, 1947
 C. *argentula* (Stephens, 1834)
 cothurnella Duponchel, 1843
 C. *peisoniella* Kasy, 1965
 C. *pseudorepentis* Toll, 1960
 C. *follicularis* (Vallot, 1802)
 troglodytella Duponchel, 1843
 C. *granulatella* Zeller, 1849
 albicans Zellr, 1849
 artemisiae Mühlhig, 1964
 C. *hungariae* Gozmány, 1955
 C. *pseudociconiella* Toll, 1952
 C. *tyrrhaenica* Amsel, 1952
 C. *adpersella* Benander, 1939
 C. *dianthi* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
 amseli Toll, 1942
 C. *albineella* Toll, 1960
 C. *sileneella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
 C. *ciconiella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855
 tritici Lindemann, 1881
 C. *nutantella* Mühlhig & Frey, 1857
 C. *saponariella* Heeger, 1848
 C. *musculella* Mühlhig, 1864
 C. *paripennella* Zeller, 1839
 C. *niveistrigella* Heinemann & Wocke, 1876
 muhlgiella Heinemann & Wocke, 1877
 C. *clypeiferella* O. Hofmann, 1871
 C. *binotapennella* (Duponchel, 1843)
 C. *squalorella* Zeller, 1849
 C. *salicorniae* Heinemann & Wocke, 1876
 binotapennella Stainton, 1854 auctt.
 C. *unipunctella* Zeller, 1849
 nigrostigmatella Heeger, 1853
 zelleri Nowicki, 1860

C. *preisseckeri* Toll, 1942
 C. *pilicornis* Rebel, 1914
 C. *wockeella* Zeller, 1849
 italiae Toll, 1960
 C. *onopordiella* Zeller, 1849
 eremica Amsel, 1935
 cerinaula Meyrick, 1936
 pseudophlomidella Toll, 1952
 sivandella Toll, 1959

37. MOMPHIDAE

Mompha Hübner, 1825

M. *miscella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 M. *idaei* (Zeller, 1839)
 M. *langiella* (Hübner, 1796)
 M. *terminella* (Humphreys & Westwood, 1845)
 M. *locupletella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 M. *raschkiella* (Zeller, 1838)
 M. *ochraceella* (Curtis, 1839)
 M. *lacteella* (Stephens, 1834)
 M. *propinquella* (Stainton, 1851)
 M. *divisiella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
 decorella Stephens, 1834
 M. *bradley* Riedl, 1965
 M. *sturnipennella* (Treitschke, 1833)
 nodicolella Fuchs, 1902
 M. *subbistrigella* (Haworth, 1828)
 M. *epilobiella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 fulvescens (Haworth, 1828)

38. BLASTOBASIDAE

Blastobasis Zeller, 1855

B. *phycidella* (Zeller, 1839)
 B. *huemeri* Sinev, 1994
Hypatopa Walsingham, 1907
 H. *binotella* (Thunberg, 1794)
 H. *inunctella* (Zeller, 1839)
Tecnerium Walsingham, 1908
 T. *perplexum* (Gozmány, 1957)

39. PTEROLONCHIDAE

Pterolonche Zeller, 1847

P. *albescens* Zeller, 1847
 P. *inspersa* Staudinger, 1859

40. AUTOSTICHIDAE

AUTOSTICHINAE

Deroxena Meyrick, 1913

D. *venosulella* (Möschler, 1862)

SYMMOCINAE

Oegoconia Stainton, 1854

O. *caradjai* Popescu-Gorj & Capuse, 1965
 O. *deuratella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
 O. *quadripunctata* (Haworth, 1828)

Apatema Walsingham, 1900

- A. mediopallidum* Walsingham, 1900
minor Rebel, 1916
? fasciata STT. (sic!) sensu Gozmány (1958)
A. walleyi Popescu-Gorj & Capuse, 1965

Pantacordis Gozmány, 1954

- P. pales* Gozmány, 1954

Donaspastus Gozmány, 1952

- D. pannonicus* Gozmány, 1952

HOLCOPOGONINAE

Holcopogon Staudinger, 1879

- H. bubulcellus* (Staudinger, 1859)

41. AMPHISBATIDAE

Amphisbatini

Pseudatemelia Rebel, 1910

- P. josephinae* (Toll, 1956)
P. flavifrontella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
P. subochreella (Doubleday, 1859)
panzerella sensu Stephens, 1834

Amphisbatis Zeller, 1870

- A. incongruella* Stainton, 1849

Hypercalliini

Hypercallia Stephens, 1829

- H. citrinalis* (Scopoli, 1763)
Anchinia Hübner, 1825
A. daphnella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. laurolella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854
A. cristalis (Scopoli, 1763)

42. COSMOPTERIGIDAE

CHRYSOPELHINAE

Ascalenia Wocke, 1876

- A. vanella* (Frey, 1860)

Sorhagenia Spuler, 1910

- S. janiszewskae* Riedl, 1962
S. lophyrella (Douglas, 1846)

ANTEQUERINAE

Pancalia Stephens, 1829

- P. leuwenhoekella* (Linnaeus, 1761)
P. schwarzella (Fabricius, 1798)

COSMOPTERIGINAE

Vulcaniella Riedl, 1965

- V. pomposella* (Zeller, 1839)
V. extremella (Wocke, 1871)

Isidiella Riedl, 1965

- I. nickerlii* (Nickerl, 1864)

Eteobalea Hodges, 1962

- E. anonymella* (Riedl, 1965)
E. intermediella (Riedl, 1966)
E. beata (Walsingham, 1907)

- E. gronoviella* (Scopoli, 1772)

serratella Treitschke, 1833

- E. tririvella* (Staudinger, 1871)

- E. albiapicella* (Duponchel, 1843)

- E. isabellella* (O. Costa, 1836)

Stagmatophora Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- S. heydeniella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841)

Limnaecia Stainton, 1851

- L. phragmitella* Stainton, 1851

Pyroderces Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- P. argyrogrammos* (Zeller, 1847)

- P. klimeschi* Rebel, 1938

Cosmopterix Hübner, 1825

- C. zieglerella* (Hübner, 1810)

- C. orichalcea* Stainton, 1861

druryella Zeller, 1850

- C. scribaiella* Zeller, 1850

- C. lienigiella* Lienig & Zeller, 1846

43. GELECHIIDAE

GELECHINAE

Apatetrini

Apatetris Staudinger, 1879

- A. trivittellum* (Rebel, 1903)

Anomologiini

Caulastrocecis Chrétien, 1931

- C. furfurella* (Staudinger, 1871)

Megacraspedus Zeller, 1839

- M. dolosellus* (Zeller, 1839)

- M. separatellus* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1843)

- M. binotella* (Duponchel, 1843)

- M. imparellus* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1843)

Chilophselaphus Mann, 1867

- Ch. balneariellus podolicus* Toll, 1942

- Ch. fallax* Mann, 1867

- Ch. lagopellus* Herrich-Schäffer, 1860

Aristotelia Hübner, 1825

- A. decurtella* (Hübner, 1813)

- A. decoratella* (Staudinger, 1879)

- A. ericinella* (Zeller, 1839)

- A. subdecuratella* (Stainton, 1858)

- A. subericinella* (Duponchel, 1843)

- A. brizella* (Treitschke, 1833)

- A. calastomella* (Christoph, 1872)

Chrysoesthia Hübner, 1825

- Ch. drurella* (Fabricius, 1775)

herrmannella auct.

- Ch. eppelsheimi* (Staudinger, 1885)

- Ch. sexguttella* (Thunberg, 1794)

Xystophora Wocke, 1876

- X. carchariella* (Zeller, 1839)

- X. pulveratella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)

- ? [*X. lepidolampra* (Gozmány, 1952)]^[2]

Atremaea Staudinger, 1871

- A. lonchoptera* Staudinger, 1871

Isophrictis Meyrick, 1917*I. striatella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*I. anthemidella* (Wocke, 1871)**Pyncostola Meyrick, 1917***P. bohemiella* (Nickerl, 1864)

jablonkayi Gozmány, 1954

Metzneria Zeller, 1839*M. paucipunctella* (Zeller, 1839)*M. neuropterella* (Zeller, 1839)*M. aestivella* (Zeller, 1839)

carlinella Stainton, 1851

M. lappella (Linnaeus, 1758)*M. ehikeella* Gozmány, 1954*M. metzneriella* (Stainton, 1851)*M. artificella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861)

pannonicella Rebel, 1915

M. aprilicella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)

igneella Tengström, 1859

M. subflavella Englert, 1974*M. intestinella* (Mann, 1864)*M. santolinella* (Amsel, 1936)

consimilella Hackman, 1946?

[*M. tristella* Rebel, 1901]^[3]**Apodia Heinemann, 1870***A. bifractella* (Duponchel, 1843)**Ptocheuusa Heinemann, 1870***P. paupella* (Zeller, 1847)*P. inopella* (Zeller, 1839)*P. abnormella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)**Psamathocrita Meyrick, 1925***P. osseella* (Stainton, 1860)?[*P. ? sp.* Elsner et al. 1999]^[4]**Argolamprotes Benander, 1945***A. micella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Monochroa Heinemann, 1870***M. cytisella* (Curtis, 1837)*M. rumicetella* (O. Hofmann, 1868)*M. sepicolella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)

balcanica Rebel, 1903

agasta Gozmány, 1954

M. tenebrella (Hübner, 1817)*M. servella* (Zeller, 1839)

farionosae Stainton, 1867

M. conspersella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)

questionella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854

morosa Mühlig, 1864

M. elongella (Heinemann, 1870)*M. lutulentella* (Zeller, 1839)

brunickii Rebel, 1913

M. lucidella (Stephens, 1834)*M. divisella* (Douglas, 1850)

csornensis (Rebel, 1909)

M. palustrella (Douglas, 1850)

rozsikella Rebel, 1909

M. simplicella (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)? [*M. arundinetella* (Stainton, 1858)]^[5]*M. nomadella* (Zeller, 1868)*M. hornigi* (Staudinger, 1883)*M. niphognatha* (Gozmány, 1953)*M. parvulata* Gozmány, 1957

mediterranea Nel & Luquet, 1997

? [*M. sp.* 1 Elsner et al. 1999]^[6]? [*M. sp.* 3 Elsner et al. 1999]^[7]**Eulamprotes Bradley, 1971***E. wilkella* (Linnaeus, 1758)

pictella Zeller, 1839

E. superbella (Zeller, 1839)*E. unicolorella* (Duponchel, 1843)*E. atrella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Dirhonisia Rebel, 1905***D. cervinella* (Eversmann, 1844)**Ornativalva Gozmány, 1955***O. plutelliformis* (Staudinger, 1859)**Gladivalva Sattler, 1960***G. aizpuruai* Vives, 1990**Bryotropha Heinemann, 1870***B. terrella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*B. desertella* (Douglas, 1850)*B. tachyptilella* (Rebel, 1916)? [*B. sp.* nach Elsner & Karsholt, 1999]^[8]*B. plantariella* (Tengström, 1848)*B. domestica* (Haworth, 1828)*B. senectella* (Zeller, 1839)*B. umbrosella* (Zeller, 1839)*B. affinis* (Haworth, 1828)*B. basaltinella* (Zeller, 1839)? [*B. dryadella* (Zeller, 1850)]^[9]**Teleiodini****Recurvaria Haworth, 1828***R. nanella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*R. leucatella* (Clerck, 1759)**Coleotechnites Chambers, 1880***C. piceaella* (Kearfott, 1903)**Exoteleia Wallengren, 1881***E. dodocella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**Stenolechia Meyrick, 1894***S. gemmella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**Parastenolechia Kanazawa, 1985***P. nigrinotella* (Zeller, 1847)**Stenolechoides Elsner, 1996***S. pseudogemmellus* Elsner, 1996**Parachronistis Meyrick, 1925***P. albiceps* (Zeller, 1839)**Teleiodes Sattler, 1960***T. vulgella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*T. wagaie* (Nowicki, 1860)*T. luculella* (Hübner, 1813)*T. flavimaculella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)*T. saltuum* (Zeller, 1878)

T. sequax (Haworth, 1828)
***Carpatolechia* C?puse, 1964**
C. decorella (Haworth, 1812)
 humeralis Zeller, 1839
C. aenigma (Sattler, 1983)
C. fugitivella (Zeller, 1839)
C. fugacella (Zeller, 1839)
C. alburnella (Zeller, 1839)
C. notatella (Hübner, 1813)
C. proximella (Hübner, 1796)
***Pseudotelphusa* Janse, 1958**
P. scalella (Scopoli, 1763)
P. paripunctella (Thunberg, 1794)
 triparella Zeller, 1839
P. tessella (Linnaeus, 1758)
***Streyella* Janse, 1958**
S. anguinella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861)
***Teleopsis* Sattler, 1960**
T. diffinis (Haworth, 1828)
***Xenolechia* Meyrick, 1895**
 ? [*X. aethiops* (Humphreys & Westwood, 1845)]
***Altenia* Sattler, 1960**
A. scriptella (Hübner, 1796)

Gelechiini

***Gelechia* Hübner, 1825**
G. rhombella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
G. scotinella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854
 lakatensis Rebel, 1904
G. senticetella (Staudinger, 1859)
G. sabinella Zeller, 1839
G. sororculella (Hübner, 1817)
G. muscosella Zeller, 1839
G. asinella (Hübner, 1796)
G. basipunctella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854
 albicans Heinemann, 1870
G. nigra (Haworth, 1828)
G. turpella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 pinguinella Treitschke, 1832
G. rhombelliformis Staudinger, 1871
G. sestertiella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854
***Psoricoptera* Stainton, 1854**
P. gibbosella (Zeller, 1839)
***Mirificarma* Gozmány, 1955**
M. maculatella (Hübner, 1796)
M. eburnella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 flamella (Hübner, 1825)
 formosella Hübner, 1796, nec Denis & Schiff.,
 1775
M. lentiginosella (Zeller, 1839)
M. cytisella (Treitschke, 1833)
M. mulinella (Zeller, 1839)
***Chionodes* Hübner, 1825**
Ch. lugubrella (Fabricius, 1794)
Ch. tragicella (Heyden, 1865)

Ch. luctuella (Hübner, 1793)
Ch. distinctella (Zeller, 1839)
Ch. electella (Zeller, 1839)
Ch. viduella (Fabricius, 1794)
Ch. fumatella (Douglas, 1850)
 oppletella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854
Ch. ignorantella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
***Aroga* Busck, 1914**
A. velocella (Zeller, 1839)
A. flavicomella (Zeller, 1839)
***Filatima* Busck, 1839**
F. spurcella (Duponchel, 1843)
F. tephritidella (Duponchel, 1844)
***Neofriseria* Sattler, 1960**
N. singula (Staudinger, 1876)
 suppeliella Walsingham, 1896
***Prolita* Leraut, 1993**
P. solutella (Zeller, 1839)
 pribitzeri Rebel, 1889
***Athrips* Billberg, 1820**
A. rancidella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
 triatomaea Mühlig, 1864
 vepretella Zeller, 1870
A. mouffetella (Linnaeus, 1758)
A. nigricostella (Duponchel, 1842)

Gnorimoschemini
***Gnorimoschema* Busck, 1900**
G. antiquum Povolny, 1966
G. herbichii (Nowicki, 1864)
 pazsiczkyi Rebel, 1913
***Scrobipalpa* Janse, 1951**
S. acuminatella (Sircom, 1850)
S. hungariae (Staudinger, 1871)
 ? [*S. brahmiella* (Heyden, 1862)]
S. halonella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
S. proclivella (Fuchs, 1886)
S. chrysanthemella (E. Hofmann, 1867)
 opificella Mann, 1877
S. artemisiella (Treitschke, 1833)
S. stangei (Hering, 1889)
 saltenella Mees, 1910
S. klimeschi Povolny, 1967
 ? *pauperella* (Heinemann, 1870)
S. samadensis (Pfaffenzeller, 1870)
 ? *ssp. plantaginella* (Stainton, 1883)
S. gallicella (Constant, 1885)
S. nitentella (Fuchs, 1902)
S. salinella (Zeller, 1847)
 salicorniae Hering, 1889
S. smithi Bradly & Povolny, 1964
S. obsoletella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841)
S. ocellatella (Boyd, 1858)
S. atriplicella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841)
S. murinella (Duponchel, 1843)

S. reiprichi Povolny, 1984
S. erichi Povolny, 1964
Scrobipalpus Povolny, 1964
S. psilella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
S. tussilaginis (Frey, 1867)
 tussilaginata Heinemann, 1870
Phthorimaea Meyrick, 1902
Ph. operculella (Zeller, 1873)
Ephysteris Meyrick, 1908
E. promptella (Staudinger, 1859)
E. inustella (Zeller, 1847)
Cosmardia Povolny, 1965
C. moritzella (Treitschke, 1835)
Klimeschiopsis Povolny, 1967
K. kiningerella (Duponchel, 1843)
Caryocolum Gregor & Povolny, 1954
C. fischerella (Treitschke, 1833)
 ? [*C. tischeriella* (Zeller, 1839)]
C. alsinella (Zeller, 1868)
C. viscariaella (Stainton, 1855)
C. vicinella (Douglas, 1851)
 inflatella Chrétien, 1901
C. amaurella (M. Hering, 1924)
 viscariae Schütze, 1926
C. petryi (O. Hofmann, 1899)
C. inflatvorella (Klimesch, 1938)
 sensus Gozmány, 1954
 ? [*C. cauligenella* (Schmid, 1863)]
 ? [*C. traumiella* (Zeller, 1868)]
C. leucomelanella (Zeller, 1839)
C. leucothoracellum (Klimesch, 1953)
C. marmorea (Haworth, 1828)
C. blandella (Douglas, 1852)
 maculea Haworth, 1828
C. proxima (Haworth, 1828)
 maculiferella Douglas, 1851
C. blandulella (Tutt, 1887)
C. tricolorella (Haworth, 1812)
C. junctella (Douglas, 1851)
C. huebneri (Haworth, 1828)
 knaggsiella Stainton, 1866
C. kroesmanniella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)

Anacampsini

Sophronia Hübner, 1825
S. semicostella (Hübner, 1813)
S. consanguinella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854
S. illustrella (Hübner, 1796)
S. ascalis Gozmány, 1951
 ? [*S. marginella* Toll, 1936]^[10]
S. chilonella (Treitschke, 1833)
S. humerella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
S. sicariellus (Zeller, 1839)
Stomopterix Heinemann, 1870
S. detersella (Zeller, 1847)
S. remissella (Zeller, 1847)

S. hungaricella Gozmány, 1957
Syncopacma Meyrick, 1925
S. patruella (Mann, 1857)
S. coronillella (Treitschke, 1833)
S. sangiella (Stainton, 1863)
S. cinctella (Clerck, 1759)
 vorticella Scopoli, 1763
S. wormiella (Wolff, 1958)
 ? [*S. azosterella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)]^[11]
S. ochrofasciella (Toll, 1936)
S. taeniolella (Zeller, 1839)
S. albifrontella (Heinemann, 1870)
S. cincticulella (Bruand, 1850)
S. vinella (Bankes, 1898)
S. linella (Chrétien, 1904)
 schoenmanni (Gozmány, 1957)
 ? [*S. albipalpella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)]^[12]
S. captivella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
 sarothamnella Zeller, 1868
Approaerema Durrant, 1897
A. anthyllidella (Hübner, 1813)
Iwaruna Gozmány, 1957
I. biguttella (Duponchel, 1843)
I. klimeschi Wolff, 1958
Anacampsis Curtis, 1827
A. populella (Clerck, 1759)
A. blattariella (Hübner, 1796)
 betulinella Vári, 1941
A. timidella (Wocke, 1887)
 disquei Meess, 1907
 quercella Chretien, 1907—
A. scintillella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841)
A. obscurella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
 subsequella Hübner, 1796
Mesophleps Hübner, 1825
M. silacella (Hübner, 1796)
Crossobela Meyrick, 1923
C. trinotella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856)

Chelariini

Anarsia Zeller, 1839
A. lineatella Zeller, 1839
A. spartiella (Schrank, 1802)
Hypatima Hübner, 1825
H. rhomboidella (Linnaeus, 1758)
Nothris Hübner, 1825
N. verbascella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
N. lemniscella (Zeller, 1839)
Neophaculata Gozmány, 1955
 ? [*N. ericetella* (Geyer, 1832)]^[13]
N. infernella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
Holcophora Staudinger, 1871
H. statices Staudinger, 1871

DICHOMERIDINAE

Dichomeris Hübner, 1818

D. marginella (Fabricius, 1781)
D. ustalella (Fabricius, 1794)
D. derasella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
fasciella Hübner, 1796
D. limosellus (Schläger, 1849)
D. rasilella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
D. barbella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
D. latipennella (Rebel, 1937)

***Acanthophila* Heinemann, 1870**

A. alacella (Zeller, 1839)?
A. latipennella (Rebel, 1937)

***Anaspaltis* Meyrick, 1925**

A. renigerellus (Zeller, 1839)

***Brachmia* Hübner, 1825**

B. dimidiella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
B. blandella (Fabricius, 1798)
gerronella Zeller, 1850
B. procursella Rebel, 1903
B. inortnatella (Douglas, 1850)

***Helcystogramma* Zeller, 1877**

H. lineolella (Zeller, 1839)
H. triannulella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
H. lutatella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)
H. rufescens (Haworth, 1828)
H. arulensis (Rebel, 1929)
H. albinervis (Gerasimov, 1929)

***Acompsia* Hübner, 1825**

A. cinerella (Clerck, 1759)
A. tripunctella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

PEXICOPIINAE

***Pexicopia* Common, 1958**

P. malvella (Hübner, 1805)

***Platyedra* Meyrick, 1895**

P. subcinerea (Haworth, 1828)
vilella Zeller, 1847

***Sitotroga* Heinemann, 1870**

S. cerealella (Olivier, 1789)

***Thiotricha* Meyrick, 1886**

T. subocellea (Stephens, 1834)

ZYGAENOIDEA

44. LIMACODIDAE

***Apoda* Haworth, 1809**

A. limacodes (Hufnagel, 1766)

***Heterogenea* Knoch, 1783**

H. asella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

45. HETEROGYNIDAE

***Heterogynis* Rambur, 1837**

H. penella (Hübner, 1819)

46. ZYGAENIDAE

Procridinae

***Theresimima* Strand, 1917**

Th. appellophaga (Bayle-Barelle, 1808)

***Rhagades* Wallengren, 1863**

Rh. pruni ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

***Jordanita* Verity, 1946**

J. budensis (Ad. & Au. Speyer, 1858)

J. notata (Zeller, 1847)

J. subsolana (Staudinger, 1862)

J. graeca (Jordan, 1907)

J. chloros (Hübner, 1813)

J. globulariae (Hübner, 1793)

J. fazekasi Efetov, 1998

***Adscita* Retzius, 1783**

A. geryon (Hübner, 1813)

A. statices (Linnaeus, 1758)

Zygaeninae

***Zygaena* Fabricius, 1775**

Z. punctum Ochsenheimer, 1808

Z. cynarae (Esper, 1789)

Z. laeta (Hübner, 1790)

Z. brizae (Esper, 1800)

Z. minos ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Z. purpuralis (Brünnich, 1763)

Z. fausta (Linnaeus, 1767)

Z. carniolica (Scopoli, 1763)

Z. loti ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Z. osterodensis Reiss, 1921

Z. viciae ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Z. ephialtes (Linnaeus, 1767)

Z. angelicae Ochsenheimer, 1808

Z. filipendulae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Z. lonicerae (Scheven, 1777)

SESIOIDEA

47. BRACHODIDAE

***Brachodes* Guenée, 1845**

B. appendiculata (Esper, 1783)

B. nana (Treitschke, 1834)

B. pumila (Ochsenheimer, 1808)

48. SESIIDAE

Tinthiinae

Tinthiini

***Tinthia* Walker, 1865**

T. tineiformis (Esper, 1789)

T. brosisiformis (Hübner, 1813)

Pennisetiini

***Pennisetia* Dehne, 1850**

P. hylaeiformis (Laspeyres, 1801)

Sesiinae

Sesiini

***Sesia* Fabricius, 1775**

S. apiformis (Clerck, 1759)

Paranthrenini

Paranthrene Hübner, 1819

- P. tabaniformis* (Rottemburg, 1775)
P. insolita polonica Schnaider, 1939

Synanthedonini

Synanthedon Hübner, 1819

- S. spheciformis* ([Denis & Schiff., 1775)
S. stomoxiformis (Hübner, 1790)
S. mesiaeformis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1846)
S. culiciformis (Linnaeus, 1758)
S. formicaeformis (Esper, 1783)
S. adrenaeformis (Laspeyres, 1801)
S. melliniformis (Laspeyres, 1801)
S. vespiformis (Linnaeus, 1761)
S. myopaeformis (Borkhausen, 1789)
S. conopiformis (Esper, 1782)
S. tipuliformis (Clerck, 1759)
S. cephiformis (Ochsenheimer, 1808)
S. loranthi (Kralicek, 1966)
S. spuleri (Fuchs, 1908)

Bembecia Hübner, 1819

- B. ichneumoniformis* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
B. albanensis (Rebel, 1918)
B. scopigera (Scopoli, 1763)
B. megillaeformis (Hübner, 1813)
B. puella Laštuvka, 1989
B. uroceriformis (Treitschke, 1834)

Synansphecica Capuse, 1973

- S. triannuliformis* (Freyer, 1845)
S. muscaeformis (Esper, 1783)
S. affinis (Staudinger, 1856)

Chamaesphecica Spuler, 1910

- Ch. anatolica* Schwingenschuss, 1938
Ch. aerifrons (Zeller, 1847)
Ch. nigrifrons (Le Cerf, 1911)
Ch. alysoniformis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1846)
Ch. chalciformis (Esper, 1804)
Ch. colpiformis (Staudinger, 1856)
Ch. annellata (Zeller, 1847)
Ch. dumonti Le Cerf, 1922
Ch. masariformis (Ochsenheimer, 1808)
Ch. bibioniformis (Esper, 1800)
Ch. astatiformis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1846)
Ch. euceraeformis (Ochsenheimer, 1816)
Ch. palustris Kautz, 1927
Ch. tenthrediniformis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Ch. empiformis (Esper, 1783)
Ch. hungarica (Tomala, 1901)
Ch. crassicornis Bartel, 1912
Ch. leucopsiformis (Esper, 1800)

COSSOIDEA

49. COSSIDAE

Cossinae

Cossus Fabricius, 1794

- C. cossus* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Lamellocossus Daniel, 1956
L. terebrus ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Parahypopta Daniel, 1961
P. caestrum (Hübner, 1808)
Catopta Staudinger, 1899
C. thrips (Hübner, 1818)
Dyspessa Hübner, 1820
D. ulula (Borkhausen, 1790)
Zeuzerinae
Zeuzera Latreille, 1804
Z. pyrina (Linnaeus, 1761)
Phragmataecia Newman, 1850
Ph. castaneae (Hübner, 1790)

TORTRICOIDEA

50. TORTRICIDAE

Tortricinae

Cochylini

Phtheochroa Stephens, 1829

- Ph. inopiana* (Haworth, 1811)
Ph. schreibersiana (Frölich, 1828)
Ph. pulvillana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
Ph. sodaliana (Haworth, 1811)
Ph. fulvicinctana (Constant, 1893)
Ph. procerana (Lederer, 1853)
Ph. purana (Guenée, 1845)
Ph. duponchelana (Duponchel, 1843)
Ph. annae Huemer, 1990

Hysterochroa Obratzov, 1944

- H. maculosana* (Haworth, 1811)
Cochylimorpha Razowski, 1959
C. hilarana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
C. jaculana (Snellen, 1883)
C. clavana (Constant, 1888)
C. elongana (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
C. woliniana (Schleich, 1868)
C. obliquana (Eversmann, 1844)
C. jucundana (Treitschke, 1835)
C. straminea (Haworth, 1811)
C. alternana (Stephens, 1834)

Phalonidia Le Marchand, 1933

- Ph. gilvicomana* (Zeller, 1847)
Ph. curvistrigana (Stainton, 1859)
Ph. manniana (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
Ph. affinitana (Douglas, 1846)
Ph. albipalpata (Zeller, 1847)
Ph. contractana (Zeller, 1847)
Gynnidomorpha Turner, 1967
G. luridana (Gregson, 1870)
G. vectisana (Humpreys & Westwood, 1845)
G. permixtana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Agapeta Hübner, 1825

- A. hamana* (Linnaeus, 1758)
A. zoegana (Linnaeus, 1767)

Fulvoclysia **Obraztsov, 1943***F. nerminalae* Kocak, 1982**Eugnota** **Hübner, 1825***E. lathoniana* (Hübner, 1800)*E. magnificana* (Rebel, 1914)**Prochlidonia** **Razowski, 1960***P. amiantana* (Hübner, 1799)**Eupoecilia** **Stephens, 1829***E. angustana* (Hübner, 1799)*E. ambiguella* (Hübner, 1796)**Aethes** **Billberg, 1820***A. hartmanniana* (Clerck, 1758)*A. piercei* (Obraztsov, 1952)*A. williana* (Brahm, 1791)*A. margarotana* (Duponchel, 1836)*A. moribundana* (Staudinger, 1859)*A. nefandana* (Kennel, 1899)*A. triangulana* (Treitschke, 1835)*A. rutilana* (Hübner, 1817)*A. smeathmanniana* (Fabricius, 1781)*A. tessarana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. sanguinana* (Treitschke, 1830)*A. dilucidana* (Stephens, 1852)*A. flagellana* (Duponchel, 1836)*A. beatricella* (Walsingham, 1808)*A. vicinana* (Mann, 1859)*A. francillana* (Fabricius, 1794)*A. bilbaensis* (Rössler, 1877)*A. tornella* (Walsingham, 1898)*A. cnicana* (Westwood, 1854)*A. rubigana* (Treitschke, 1830)*A. kindermanniana* (Treitschke, 1830)**Cochylidia** **Obraztsov, 1956***C. rupicola* (Curtis, 1834)*C. subroseana* (Haworth, 1811)*C. richteriana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837)*C. moguntiana* (Rössler, 1864)*C. heydeniana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)*C. implicatana* (Wocke, 1856)**Diceratura** **Djakonov, 1929***D. roseofasciana* (Mann, 1855)*D. ostrinana* (Guenée, 1845)**Cochylis** **Treitschke, 1830***C. roseana* (Haworth, 1811)*C. flaviciliana* (Westwood, 1854)*C. epilinana* Duponchel, 1842*C. hybridella* (Hübner, 1813)*C. salebrana* (Mann, 1862)*C. dubitana* (Hübner, 1799)*C. atricapitana* (Stephens, 1852)*C. pallidana* Zeller, 1847*C. posterana* Zeller, 1847**Cryptocochylis** **Razowski, 1960***C. conjunctana* (Mann, 1864)**Falseuncaria** **Obraztsov & Swatschek, 1958***F. degreyana* (McLachlan, 1869)*F. ruficiliana* (Haworth, 1811)**Tortricini****Spatalistis** **Meyrick, 1907***S. bifasciana* (Hübner, 1787)**Tortrix** **Linnaeus, 1758***T. viridana* Linnaeus, 1758**Aleimma** **Hübner, 1825***A. loeflingiana* (Linnaeus, 1758)**Acleris** **Hübner, 1825***A. holmiana* (Linnaeus, 1758)*A. forsskaleana* (Linnaeus, 1758)*A. bergmanniana* (Linnaeus, 1758)*A. sparsana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. rhombana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. emargana* (Fabricius, 1775)*A. schalleriana* (Linnaeus, 1761)*A. lorquiniana* (Duponchel, 1835)*A. umbrana* (Hübner, 1799)*A. cristana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. variegana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. shepherdana* (Stephens, 1852)*A. hastiana* (Linnaeus, 1775)*A. hippophaeana* (Heyden, 1865)*A. permutana* (Duponchel, 1836)*A. scabrana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. ferrugana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. notana* (Donovan, 1806)*A. quercinana* (Zeller, 1849)*A. logiana* (Clerck, 1759)*A. roscidana* (Hübner, 1799)*A. literana* (Linnaeus, 1758)*A. lipsiana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. rufana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*A. fimbriana* (Thunberg, 1791)**Cnephasiini****Xerocnephasia** **Leraut, 1979***X. rigana* (Sodoffsky, 1829)**Neosphaleroptera** **Réal, 1953***N. nubilana* (Hübner, 1799)**Oporopsamma** **Gozmány, 1954***O. wertheimsteini* (Rebel, 1913)**Doloploca** **Hübner, 1825***D. punctulana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Tortricodes** **Guenée, 1845***T. alternella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Eana** **Billberg, 1820***E. osseana* (Scopoli, 1763)*E. argentana* (Clerck, 1759)*E. canescana* (Guenée, 1845)*E. hungariae* Razowski, 1958*E. incanana* (Stephens, 1852)*E. derivana* (La Harpe, 1858)

Cnephasia Curtis, 1826

- C. incertana* (Treitschke, 1835)
C. abrasana (Duponchel, 1843)
C. stephensiana (Doubleday, 1849)
C. alticolana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
C. asseclana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. pasiuana (Hübner, 1799)
C. genitalana Pierce & Metcalfe, 1922
C. communana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
C. cupressivorana (Staudinger, 1871)
C. oxyacanthana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
C. chrysantheana (Duponchel, 1843)
C. ecullyana Réal, 1951

Sparganothini**Sparganothis Hübner, 1825**

- S. pilleriana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Euliini**Eulia Hübner, 1825**

- E. ministrana* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Pseudargyrotoza Obraztsov, 1954
P. conwagana (Fabricius, 1775)

Ramapesiini**Epagoge Hübner, 1825**

- E. grotiana* (Fabricius, 1781)
Paramesia Stephens, 1829
P. gnomana (Clerck, 1759)
Periclepsis Bradley, 1977
P. cinctana ([Denis & Schioffermüller], 1775)

Philedone Hübner, 1825

- Ph. gerningana* (Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Pseudeulia Obraztsov, 1954

- P. asinana* (Hübner, 1799)

Capua Stephens, 1834

- C. vulgana* (Frölich, 1828)
Philedonides Obraztsov, 1954
Ph. lunana (Thunberg, 1784)
Ph. rhombicana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

Archipini**Archips Hübner, 1825**

- A. oporana* (Linnaeus, 1758)
A. podana (Scopoli, 1763)
A. crataegana (Hübner, 1799)
A. xylosteana (Linnaeus, 1758)
A. rosana (Linnaeus, 1758)
Choristoneura Lederer, 1859
Ch. diversana (Hübner, 1817)
Ch. murinana (Hübner, 1799)
Ch. hebenstreitella (Müller, 1764)
Argyrotaenia Stephens, 1852
A. ljungiana (Thunberg, 1797)

Ptycholomoides Obraztsov, 1954

- P. aeriferana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

Ptycholoma Stephens, 1829

- P. lecheana* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Pandemis Hübner, 1825
P. corylana (Fabricius, 1794)
P. cerasana (Hübner, 1786)
P. heparana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
P. dumetana (Treitschke, 1835)

Syndemis Hübner, 1825

- S. musculana* (Hübner, 1799)

Lozotaenia Stephens, 1829

- L. forsterana* (Fabricius, 1781)

Aphelia Hübner, 1825

- A. paleana* (Hübner, 1793)
A. ochreana (Hübner, 1799)
A. viburnana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Dichelia Guenée, 1845

- D. histrionana* (Frölich, 1828)

Clepsia Guenée, 1845

- C. rolandriana* (Linnaeus, 1758)
C. steineriana (Hübner, 1799)
C. senecionana (Hübner, 1819)
C. rurinana (Linnaeus, 1758)
C. spectrana (Treitschke, 1830)
C. pallidana (Fabricius, 1776)
C. consimilana (Hübner, 1817)

Adoxophyes Meyrick, 1881

- A. orana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1834)

Chlidanotinae**Olindia Guenée, 1845**

- O. schumacherana* (Fabricius, 1787)

Isotrias Meyrick, 1895

- I. hybridana* (Hübner, 1817)
I. rectifasciana (Haworth, 1811)

Olethreutinae**Bactrini****Bactra Stephens, 1834**

- B. lancealana* (Hübner, 1799)
B. furfurana (Haworth, 1811)
B. lacteana (Caradja, 1916)
B. robustana (Christoph, 1872)

Endotheniini**Endothenia Stephens, 1852**

- E. gentianaeana* (Hübner, 1799)
E. oblongana (Haworth, 1811)
E. marginana (Haworth, 1811)
E. ustulana (Haworth, 1811)
E. lapideana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
E. nigricostana (Haworth, 1811)
E. quadrimaculana (Haworth, 1811)
E. sororiana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)

Olethreutini

Eudemis Hübner, 1825

- E. porphyra* (Hübner, 1799)
E. profundana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Aterpia Guenée, 1845

- A. corticana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Selenodes Guenée, 1845

- S. karelica* (Tengström, 1875)

Pseudosciaphila Obratzsov, 1966

- P. branderiana* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Apotomis Hübner, 1825

- A. semifasciana* (Haworth, 1811)
A. lineana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. inudana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. turbidana (Hübner, 1825)
A. betuletana (Haworth, 1811)
A. capreana (Hübner, 1817)
A. sororculana (Zetterstedt, 1839)
A. sauciana (Frölich, 1828)

Orthotaenia Stephens, 1829

- O. undulana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Hedya Hübner, 1825

- H. salicella* (Linnaeus, 1758)
H. nubiferana (Haworth, 1811)
H. pruniana (Hübner, 1799)
H. dimidiana (Clerck, 1759)
H. ochroleucana (Frölich, 1828)

Celypha Hübner, 1825

- C. rufana* (Scopoli, 1763)
C. striana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. rurestrana (Duponchel, 1843)
C. capreolana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
C. flavipalpna (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
C. woodiana (Barrett, 1882)
C. cespitana (Hübner, 1817)
C. lacunana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. siderana (Treitschke, 1835)
C. rivulana (Scopoli, 1763)
C. doubledayana (Barrett, 1872)

Phiaris Hübner, 1825

- Ph. umbrosana* (Freyer, 1842)
Ph. obsoletana (Zetterstedt, 1839)
Ph. stibiana (Guenée, 1845)
Ph. scoriana (Guenée, 1845)

Capricornia Obratzsov, 1960

- C. boisduvaliana* (Duponchel, 1836)

Pristerognatha Obratzsov, 1960

- P. penthinana* (Guenée, 1845)

Cymolomia Lederer, 1859

- C. hartigiana* (Saxesen, 1840)

Olethreutes Hübner, 1822

- O. arcuella* (Clerck, 1759)

Piniphila Falkovitsh, 1962

- P. bifasciana* (Haworth, 1811)

Pseudohermenias Obratzsov, 1960

- P. abietana* (Fabricius, 1787)

Pelatea Guenée, 1845

- P. klugiana* (Freyer, 1834)

Lobesiini

Lobesia Guenée, 1845

- L. euphorbiana* (Freyer, 1842)
L. botrana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
L. abscisana (Doubleday, 1849)
L. reliquana (Hübner, 1825)
L. bicinctana (Duponchel, 1844)
L. artemisiana (Zeller, 1847)
L. confinitana (Staudinger, 1870)

Eucosmini

Eriopsela Guenée, 1845

- E. quadrana* (Hübner, 1813)

Thiodia Hübner, 1825

- Th. torridana* (Lederer, 1859)
Th. lerneana Treitschke, 1835
Th. citrana (Staudinger, 1871)
Th. trochilana (Frölich, 1828)

Rhopobota Lederer, 1859

- Rh. myrtillana* (Humphreys & Westwood, 1845)
Rh. stagnana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Rh. naevana (Hübner, 1817)

Spilonota Stephens, 1829

- S. ocellana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

- S. laricana* (Heinemann, 1863)

Gibberifera Obratzsov, 1946

- G. simplana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1836)

Epinotia Hübner, 1825

- E. sordidana* (Hübner, 1824)
E. trigonella (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. brunnichiana (Linnaeus, 1767)
E. maculana (Fabricius, 1775)
E. solandriana (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. abbreviana (Fabricius, 1794)
E. festivana (Hübner, 1799)
E. granitana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
E. signatana (Douglas, 1845)
E. cruciana (Linnaeus, 1761)
E. immundana (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
E. thapsiana (Zeller, 1847)
E. crenana (Hübner, 1799)
E. kochiana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
E. nanana (Treitschke, 1835)
E. huebneriana Kocak, 1980
ustulana Hübner, 1813
E. demarniana (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1840)
E. subocellana (Donovan, 1806)
E. tetraquatrana (Haworth, 1811)
E. pygmaeana (Hübner, 1799)
E. tenerana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
E. ramella (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. nigricana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

E. rubiginosana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
E. pusillana (Peyerimhoff, 1863)
E. tedella (Clerck, 1759)
E. bilunana (Haworth, 1811)
E. nisella (Clerck, 1759)
E. hungaricana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
Zeiraphera Treitschke, 1829
Z. griseana (Hübner, 1799)
Z. rufimitrana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
Z. isertana (Fabricius, 1794)
Crociosema Zeller, 1847
C. plebejana Zeller, 1847
Phaneta Stephens, 1852
Ph. pauperana (Duponchel, 1843)
Pelochrista Lederer, 1859
P. decolorana (Freyer, 1842)
P. caecimaculana (Hübner, 1799)
P. mollitana (Zeller, 1847)
P. modicana (Zeller, 1847)
P. subtiliana (Jäckh, 1960)
P. infidana (Hübner, 1824)
P. latericiana (Rebel, 1919)
P. hepatariana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
P. arabescana (Eversmann, 1844)
Eucosma Hübner, 1823
E. obumbratana (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)
E. cumulana (Guenée, 1845)
E. cana (Haworth, 1811)
E. hohenwartiana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
E. jaceana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
E. fulvana (Stephens, 1834)
E. conformana (Mann, 1872)
E. balatonana (Osthelder, 1937)
E. campoliliana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
E. aemulana (Schläger, 1849)
E. lacteana (Treitschke, 1835)
E. albidulana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
E. fervidana (Zeller, 1847)
E. metzneriana (Treitschke, 1830)
E. tundrana (Kennel, 1900)
E. messingiana (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837)
E. wimmerana (Treitschke, 1835)
E. conterminana (Guenée, 1845)
E. aspidiscana (Hübner, 1817)
E. pupillana (Clerck, 1759)
E. lugubrana (Treitschke, 1830)
Epibactra Ragonot, 1894
E. sareptana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861)
Gyponoma Meyrick, 1895
G. minutana (Hübner, 1799)
G. dealbana (Frölich, 1828)
G. oppressana (Treitschke, 1835)
G. sociana (Haworth, 1811)
G. nitidulana (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)
G. aceriana (Duponchel, 1843)

Epiblema Hübner, 1825
E. sticticana (Fabricius, 1794)
E. scutulana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
E. cnicicolana (Zeller, 1847)
E. foenella (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. junctana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856)
E. hepaticana (Treitschke, 1835)
E. turbidana (Treitschke, 1835)
E. grandaevana (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)
E. graphana (Treitschke, 1835)
E. mendiculana (Treitschke, 1835)
E. similana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
E. obscurana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
E. praefractana (Kennel, 1901)
Notocelia Hübner, 1825
N. cynosbatella (Linnaeus, 1758)
N. uddmanniana (Linnaeus, 1758)
N. roborana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
N. incarnatana (Hübner, 1800)
N. trimaculana (Haworth, 1811)
Blastesthia Obratzov, 1960
B. turionella (Linnaeus, 1758)
Retinia Guenée, 1845
R. resinella (Linnaeus, 1758)
Gravitarata Obratzov, 1946
G. margarotana (Heinemann, 1863)
Rhyacionia Hübner, 1825
Rh. buoliana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Rh. pinicolana (Doubleday, 1849)
Rh. piniana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
Eucosmomorpha Obratzov, 1951
E. albersana (Hübner, 1813)
Enarmonia Hübner, 1826
E. formosana (Scopoli, 1763)
Ancylis Hübner, 1825
A. uncella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. laetana (Fabricius, 1775)
A. obtusana (Haworth, 1811)
A. comptana (Frölich, 1828)
A. upupana (Treitschke, 1835)
A. geminana (Donovan, 1806)
A. subarcuana (Douglas, 1847)
inornatana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
A. diminutana (Haworth, 1811)
A. selenana (Guenée, 1845)
A. unculana (Haworth, 1811)
A. apicella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. poludana Barrett, 1886
A. badiana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. achatana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. mitterbacheriana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. tineana (Hübner, 1799)

Grapholitini

Cydia Hübner, 1825

- C. fissana* (Frölich, 1828)
C. compositella (Fabricius, 1775)
C. delineaana (Walker, 1863)
C. pallifrontana (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)
C. difficilana (Walsingham, 1900)
C. coronillana (Lienig & Zeller,
C. caecana (Schläger, 1847)
C. discretana (Wocke, 1861)
C. gemmiferana (Treitschke, 1835)
C. larseni (Rebel, 1903)
C. nebritana (Treitschke, 1830)
C. jungiella (Linnaeus, 1761)
C. lathyrana (Hübner, 1822)
C. orobana (Treitschke, 1830)
C. funebrana (Treitschke, 1835)
C. tenebrosana (Duponchel, 1843)
C. janthinana (Duponchel, 1843)
C. lobarzewskii (Nowicki, 1860)
C. molesta (Busck, 1916)
C. nigricana (Fabricius, 1794)
C. oxytropidis (Martini, 1912)
C. succedana ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. medicaginis (Kuznetsov, 1962)
C. microgrammana (Guenée, 1845)
C. duplicana (Zetterstedt, 1839)
C. illutana (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)
C. conicolana (Heylaerts, 1874)
C. corollana (Hübner, 1823)
C. coniferana (Saxesen, 1840)
C. cosmophorana (Treitschke, 1835)
C. strobilella (Linnaeus, 1758)
C. pactolana (Zeller, 1840)
C. pomonella (Linnaeus, 1758)
C. zebeana (Ratzenburg, 1840)
C. pyrivora (Danilevsky, 1947)
C. servillana (Duponchel, 1836)
C. exquisitana (Rebel, 1889)
C. leguminana (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)
C. splendana (Hübner, 1799)
C. fagiglandana (Zeller, 1841)
C. amplana (Hübner, 1800)
C. inquinatana (Hübner, 1800)

Selania Stephens, 1834

- S. leplastriana* (Curtis, 1831)

Lathronympha Meyrick, 1926

- L. strigana* (Fabricius, 1775)

Pammene Hübner, 1825

- P. aurana* (Fabricius, 1775)
P. gallicana (Guenée, 1845)
P. querceti Gozmány, 1957
P. fasciana (Linnaeus, 1761)
P. splendidulana (Guenée, 1845)
P. insulana (Guenée, 1845)

- P. ignorata* Kuznetsov, 1968

- P. gallicolana* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

- P. inquilina* T. Fletcher, 1938

- P. suspectana* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

- P. albuginana* (Guenée, 1845)

- P. obscurana* (Stephens, 1834)

- P. rhediella* (Clerck, 1759)

- P. spiniana* (Duponchel, 1843)

- P. trauniana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

- P. christophana* (Möschler, 1862)

- P. regiana* (Zeller, 1849)

- P. aurita* Razowski, 1991

- P. ochsenheimeriana* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

- P. germana* (Hübner, 1799)

Strophedra Herrich-Schäffer, 1853

- S. weirana* (Douglas, 1850)

- S. nitidana* (Fabricius, 1794)

Dichrorampha Guenée, 1845

- D. gruneriana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

- D. podoliensis* (Toll, 1942)

- D. plumbana* (Scopoli, 1763)

- D. aeratana* (Pierce & Metcalfe, 1915)

- D. cacaleana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

- D. consortana* (Stephens, 1852)

- D. acuminatana* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)

- D. simplicana* (Haworth, 1811)

- D. sequana* (Hübner, 1799)

- D. heegerana* (Duponchel, 1843)

- D. senectana* Guenée, 1845

- D. gueneana* Obratsov, 1953

- D. flavidorsana* Knaggs, 1867

- D. alpinana* (Treitschke, 1830)

- D. petiverella* (Linnaeus, 1758)

- D. obscuratana* (Wolff, 1955)

- D. cinerosana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

- D. montanana* (Duponchel, 1843)

- D. agilana* (Tengström, 1848)

- D. distinctana* (Heinemann, 1863)

CHOREUTOIDEA

51. CHOREUTIDAE

Millierinae

Millieria Ragonot, 1874

- M. dolosalis* (Heydenreich, 1851)

CHOREUTINAE

Anthophila Haworth, 1811

- A. fabriciana* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Prochoreutis Diakonoff & Heppner, 1980

- P. myllerana* (Fabricius, 1794)

- P. sehestediana* (Fabricius, 1776)

- P. stellaris* (Zeller, 1847)

Tebenna Billberg, 1820

- T. bjerkanrellana* (Thunberg, 1784)

- T. micalis* (Mann, 1857)

Choreutis Hübner, 1825*Ch. pariana* (Clerck, 1759)

URODOIDEA

52. URODIDAE**Wockia Heinemann, 1870***W. asperipunctella* (Bruand, 1851)

SCHRECKENSTEINIOIDEA

53. SCHRECKENSTEINIIDAE**Schreckensteinia Hübner, 1825***Sch. festaliella* (Hübner, 1819)

EPERMENIOIDEA

54. EPERMENIIDAE**Epermenia Hübner, 1824***E. insecurella* (Stainton, 1849)*E. strictella* (Wocke, 1867)*E. aequidentella* (E. Hofmann, 1867)*E. chaerophyllella* (Goeze, 1783)*E. illigerella* (Hübner, 1813)*E. petrusella* (Heylaerts, 1883)*E. pontificella* (Hübner, 1796)**Ochromolopis Hübner, 1825***O. ictella* (Hübner, 1813)

ALUCITOIDEA

55. ALUCITIDAE**Alucita Linnaeus, 1758***A. cymatodactyla* Zeller, 1852*A. hexadactyla* Linnaeus, 1758*A. huebneri* Wallengren, 1859*A. grammodactyla* Zeller, 1841*A. desmodactyla* Zeller, 1847**Pteropteryx Hannemann, 1959***P. dodecadactyla* Hübner, 1813

PTEROPHOROIDEA

56. PTEROPHORIDAE

PTEROPHORINAE

Pterophorini**Pterophorus Geoffroy, 1762***P. ischnodactylus* (Treitschke, 1835)*P. pentadactylus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**Merrifieldia Tutt, 1905***M. baliodactyla* (Zeller, 1841)*M. malacadactyla* (Zeller, 1847)

transdanubinus (Fazekas, 1986)

M. leucodactyla ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*M. tridactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758)**Wheeleria Tutt, 1905***W. obsoleta* (Zeller, 1841)**Porritia Tutt, 1905***P. galactodactyla* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Calyphora Kasy, 1960***C. albodactyla* (Fabricius, 1794)

xanthodactylus auct. nec (Treitschke, 1833)

xerodactylus (Zeller, 1841)

C. nephelodactyla (Eversmann, 1844)*C. xanthodactyla* (Treitschke, 1833)

klimeschi Kasy, 1960

Oidaematophorini**Pselnophorus Wallengren, 1881***P. heterodactylus* (Müller, 1764)

brachydactyla Kollar, 1832

Emmelina Tutt, 1905*E. monodactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758)*E. argoteles* (Meyrick, 1922)

jezonicus (Matsumura, 1931)

pseudojezonica Derra, 1987

Adaina Tutt, 1905*A. microdactyla* (Hübner, 1813)**Hellinsia Tutt, 1905***H. tephrodactyla* (Hübner, 1813)*H. didactylites* (Ström, 1783)

scarodactyla (Hübner, 1813)

H. distincta (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)*H. lienigiana* (Zeller, 1852)

septodactyla (Treitschke, 1833)

H. osteodactyla (Zeller, 1841)*H. carphodactyla* (Hübner, 1813)*H. inulae* (Zeller, 1852)**Oidaematophorus Wallengren, 1862***O. constantii* (Ragonot, 1875)*O. lithodactyla* (Treitschke, 1833)

AGDISTINAE

Agdistis Hübner, [1825] 1816*A. heydeni* (Zeller, 1852)*A. adactyla* Hübner, [1819] 1796*A. intermedia* Caradja, 1920

hungarica Amsel, 1955

A. tamaricis (Zeller, 1847)

PLATYPTILIINAE

Platyptilia Hübner, [1825]*P. gonodactyla* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)? [*P. calodactyla*] ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)^[14]*P. nemoralis* Zeller, 1841*P. farfarella* Zeller, 1867*P. tesseradactyla* (Linnaeus, 1761)**Buszkoiana Kocak, 1981***B. capnodactyla* (Zeller, 1841)**Gillmeria Tutt, 1905***G. pallidactyla* (Haworth, 1811)*G. tetradactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758)

ochrodactyla ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

G. miantodactyla (Zeller, 1841)**Amblyptilia Hübner, [1825] 1816**

A. acanthadactyla (Hübner, [1813] 1796)
A. punctidactyla (Haworth, 1811)
cosmodactyla Hübner, 1819
Stenoptilia Hübner, [1825] 1816
S. pterodactyla (Linnaeus, 1761)
S. stigmatoides Sutter & Skyva, 1992
S. stigmatodactyla (Zeller, 1852)
S. bipunctidactyla (Scopoli, 1763)
S. annadactyla Sutter, 1988
S. gratiolae Gibeaux & Nel, 1990
S. pelidnodactyla (Stein, 1837)
S. coprodactyla (Stainton, 1851)
?[*S. graphodactyla* (Treitschke, 1833)]
S. zophodactyla (Duponchel, 1840)
S. pneumonanthes (Büttner, 1880)
Cnaemidophorus Wallengren, 1859
C. rhododactylus ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Marasmarcha Meyrick, 1886
M. lunaedactyla (Haworth, 1811)
Oxyptilus Zeller, 1841
O. pilosellae (Zeller, 1841)
O. parvidactylus (Haworth, 1811)
O. chrysodactylus ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Crombrugghia Tutt, 1906
C. distans (Zeller, 1847)
C. tristis (Zeller, 1841)
Geina Tutt, 1906
G. didactyla (Linnaeus, 1758)
Capperia Tutt, 1905
C. britanniodactyla (Gregson, 1869)
C. celeusi (Frey, 1886)
C. trichodactyla ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Stangeia Tutt, 1906
S. siceliota (Zeller, 1847)

COPROMORPHOIDEA

57. CARPOSINIDAE

Carposina Herrich-Schäffer, 1853
C. scirrhosella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854
C. berberidella Herrich-Schäffer, 1854

THYRIDOIDEA

58. THYRIDIDAE

Thyris Laspeyres, 1803
Th. fenestrella (Scopoli, 1763)
? ssp. *seminigra* Issekutz, 1953

PYRALOIDEA

59. PYRALIDAE

GALLERIINAE

Tirathabini

Aphomia Hübner, 1825
A. sociella (Linnaeus, 1758)
A. foedella (Zeller, 1839)
A. zelleri Joannis, 1932

Lamoria Walker, 1863

L. anella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Paralipsa Butler, 1879
P. gularis (Zeller, 1877)

Galleriini

Achroia Hübner, 1819
A. grisella (Fabricius, 1794)
Galleria Fabricius, 1798
G. mellonella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Pyralinae

Pyralini

Synaphe Hübner, 1825
S. moldavica (Esper, 1794)
S. bombycalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
S. antennalis (Fabricius, 1794)
S. punctalis (Fabricius, 1775)
Pyralis Linnaeus, 1758
P. regalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
P. farinalis (Linnaeus, 1758)
P. perversalis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849)
Aglossa Latreille, 1796
A. signicostalis Staudinger, 1871
A. caprealis (Hübner, 1809)
A. pinguinalis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Actenia Guenée, 1854
A. brunnealis (Treitschke, 1829)
A. honestalis (Treitschke, 1829)
Hypsopygia Hübner, 1825
H. costalis (Fabricius, 1775)
Herculia Walker, 1859
H. fulvociliialis (Duponchel, 1834)
H. incarnatalis (Zeller, 1847)
H. rubidalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Orthopygia Ragonot, 1890
O. glaucinalis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Endotrichini

Endotricha Zeller, 1847
E. flammealis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Phycitinae

Cryptoblabini

Cryptoblabes Zeller, 1848
C. bistriga (Haworth, 1811)

Phycitini

Trachonitis Zeller, 1848
T. cristella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Salebriopsis Hannemann, 1965
S. albicilla (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849)
Elegia Ragonot, 1887
E. fallax (Staudinger, 1881)
E. similella (Zincken, 1818)

Ortholepis Ragonot, 1887*O. betulae* (Goeze, 1778)**Pyla Grote, 1882***P. fusca* (Haworth, 1811)**Pempeliella Caradja, 1916***P. ornata* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*P. dilutella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*P. sororiella* (Zeller, 1839)**Catastia Hübner, 1825***C. marginea* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Khorassania Amsel, 1951***Kh. compositella* (Treitschke, 1835)**Serrulacera Amsel, 1955***S. serraticornella* (Zeller, 1839)*gregella* (Eversmann, 1844)**Sciota Hulst, 1888***S. fumella* (Eversmann, 1844)*S. rhenella* (Zincken, 1818)*S. hostilis* (Stephens, 1834)*? ssp. betuleti* Gozmány, 1953*S. adelphella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1836)**Selagia Hübner, 1825***S. argyrella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*S. spadicella* (Hübner, 1796)**Pima Hulst, 1888***P. boisduvaliella* (Guenée, 1845)**Etiella Zeller, 1839***E. zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832)**Oncocera Stephens, 1829***O. semirubella* (Scopoli, 1763)*O. faecella* (Zeller, 1839)*O. combustella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)**Pempelia Hübner, 1825***P. geminella* (Eversmann, 1844)*P. albariella* Zeller, 1839*P. formosa* (Haworth, 1811)*P. palumbella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*P. obductella* Zeller, 1839**Psorosa Zeller, 1846***P. dahliella* (Treitschke, 1832)**Dioryctria Zeller, 1846***D. sylvestrella* (Ratzeburg, 1840)*splendidella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1848*D. schuetzeella* Fuchs, 1903*D. simplicella* Heinemann, 1863*mutatella* Fuchs, 1903*D. abietella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Phycita Curtis, 1828***Ph. metzneri* (Zeller, 1846)*Ph. meliella* (Mann, 1864)*Ph. roborella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*spissicella* (Fabricius, 1777)**Hypochalcia Hübner, 1796***H. dignella* (Hübner, 1796)*H. decorella* (Hübner, 1810)*? [H. griseoanella* Ragonot, 1887]^[19]*H. lignella* (Hübner, 1796)*H. ahenella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*rubiginella* Treitschke, 1833*H. bruandella* (Guenée, 1845)*affiniella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1849**Epischnia Hübner, 1825***E. prodromella* (Hübner, 1799)**Nephopterix Hübner, 1825***N. angustella* (Hübner, 1796)**Conobathra Meyrick, 1886***C. tumidana* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)*C. repandana* (Fabricius, 1798)*tumidella* Zincken, 1818**Trachycera Ragonot, 1893***T. advenella* (Zincken, 1818)*T. suavella* (Zincken, 1818)*T. legatea* (Haworth, 1811)*legatella* Hübner, 1796*T. dulcella* (Zeller, 1848)*T. marmorea* (Haworth, 1811)**Acrobasis Zeller, 1839***A. sodalella* Zeller, 1848*A. consociella* (Hübner, 1813)*A. glaucella* Staudinger, 1859*A. obtusella* (Hübner, 1796)**Apomyelois Heinrich, 1956***A. bistriatella* (Hulst, 1887)*neophanes* (Durrant, 1915)*A. ceratoniae* (Zeller, 1839)**Glyptoteles Zeller, 1848***G. leucacrinella* Zeller, 1848**Episcythrastis Meyrick, 1937***E. tetricella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)**Eurhodope Hübner, 1825***E. rosella* (Scopoli, 1763)**Kyra Gozmány, 1958***K. cirrigerella* (Zincken, 1818)**Myelois Hübner, 1825***M. circumvoluta* (Fourcroy, 1785)*cribrella* Hübner, 1796**Pterothrixidia Amsel, 1954***P. rufella* (Duponchel, 1836)*P. impurella* (Duponchel, 1836)**Isauria Ragonot, 1887***I. dilucidella* (Duponchel, 1836)*ilignella* Zeller, 1839**Eucarphia Hübner, 1825***E. vinetella* (Fabricius, 1787)**Asarta Zeller, 1848?***[A. alpicolella* (Zeller, 1839)]**Hyporatasa Rebel, 1901***H. allotriella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)**Gymnancyla Zeller, 1848***G. canella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

G. hornigi (Lederer, 1852)
Zophodia Hübner, 1825?
[Z. grossulariella (Hübner, 1809)]^[18]
 convolutella Hübner, 1796 nom paeocc.
Eccopisa Zeller, 1848
E. effractella Zeller, 1848
Assara Walker, 1863
A. terebrella (Zincken, 1818)
Euzophera Zeller, 1867
E. pinguis (Haworth, 1811)
E. bigella (Zeller, 1848)
E. cinerosella (Zeller, 1839)
E. fuliginosella (Heinemann, 1865)
Euzopherodes Hampson, 1899
E. charlottae (Rebel, 1914)
E. vapidella (Mann, 1857)
Nyctegretis Zeller, 1848
N. lineana (Scopoli, 1786)
N. triangulella Ragonot, 1901
Ancylosis Zeller, 1839
A. cinnamomella (Duponchel, 1836)
A. sarepiella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1861)
A. roscidella (Eversmann, 1844)
A. albidella (Ragonot, 1888)
A. oblitella (Zeller, 1848)
A. deserticola (Staudinger, 1870)
Homoeosoma Curtis, 1833
H. sinuella (Fabricius, 1794)
H. inustella Ragonot, 1884
H. nebulella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
H. subalbatella (Mann, 1864)
H. nimbella (Duponchel, 1837)
Ectohomoeosoma Roesler, 1965
E. kasyellum Roesler, 1965
Phycitodes Hampson, 1917
Ph. maritima (Tengström, 1848)
Ph. binaevella (Hübner, 1813)
Ph. lacteella (Rothschild, 1915)
Ph. inquinatella (Ragonot, 1887)
Ph. albatella (Ragonot, 1887)
Vitula Ragonot, 1887
V. biviella (Zeller, 1848)
Plodia Guenée, 1845
P. interpunctella (Hübner, 1813)
Ephestia Guenée, 1845
E. kuehniella Zeller, 1879
E. welseriella (Zeller, 1848)
E. elutella (Hübner, 1796)
E. parasitella Staudinger, 1859
Cadra Walker, 1864
C. furcatella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849)
 afflatella Mann, 1855
C. figulilella (Gregson, 1871)
C. cautella (Walker, 1863)

Anerastiini
Anerastia Hübner, 1825
A. lotella (Hübner, 1813)
A. dubis Gerasimov, 1929
Hypsotropa Zeller, 1848
H. unipunctella Ragonot, 1888
Ematheudes Zeller, 1867
E. punctella (Treitschke, 1833)

Scopariinae
Scoparia Haworth, 1811
S. luteoralis (Scopoli, 1772)
S. manifestella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)
S. subfusca Haworth, 1811
S. basistrigalis Knaggs, 1866
S. ambiguus (Treitschke, 1829)
S. ancipitella (La Harpe, 1855)
S. pyralella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
S. ingratella (Zeller, 1846)
Gesneria Hübner, 1825
G. centuriella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Dipleurina Chapman, 1912
D. lacustrata (Pancer, 1804)
Eudonia Billberg, 1820
E. murana (Curtis, 1827)
E. laetella (Zeller, 1846)
E. truncicolella (Stainton, 1849)
E. mercurella (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. sudetica (Zeller, 1839)
Witlesia Chapman, 1912
W. pallida (Curtis, 1827)
Heliorthela Guenée, 1854
H. wulfeniana (Scopoli, 1763)

Crambinae
Euchromius Guenée, 1845
E. ocella (Haworth, 1811)
E. bella (Hübner, 1796)
E. superbellus (Zeller, 1849)
Chilo Zincken, 1817
Ch. phragmitella (Hübner, 1805)
Ch. luteellus (Motschulsky, 1866)
Friedlanderia Agnew, 1987
F. cicatricella (Hübner, 1824)
Calamotropha Zeller, 1863
C. paludella (Hübner, 1824)
C. aureliellus (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841)
Chrysoteuchia Hübner, 1825
Ch. culmella (Linnaeus, 1758)
Crambus Fabricius, 1798
C. pascuella (Linnaeus, 1758)
C. silvella (Hübner, 1813)
C. uliginosellus Zeller, 1850
C. ericella (Hübner, 1813)
C. pratella (Linnaeus, 1758)
C. lathonuellus (Zincken, 1817)

C. hamella (Thunberg, 1788)
C. perlella (Scopoli, 1763)^[15]
Agriphila Hübner, 1825
A. deliella (Hübner, 1813)
A. tristella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. inquinatella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. brioniellus (Zerny, 1914)
A. selasella (Hübner, 1813)
A. straminella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
A. poliellus (Treitschke, 1832)
A. tersella (Lederer, 1855)
? ssp. *hungarica* (A. Schmidt, 1909)
A. geniculea (Haworth, 1811)
A. tolli pelsonius Fazekas, 1985
Catoptria Hübner, 1825
C. permutatellus (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)
C. myella (Hübner, 1796)
C. osthelderi (Lattin, 1950)
C. mytilella (Hübner, 1805)
C. pinella (Linnaeus, 1758)
C. margaritella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. fulgidella (Hübner, 1813)
C. falsella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)^[16]
persephone Blezysnski, 1956 **syn. n.**
C. confusellus (Staudinger, 1882)
C. verellus (Zincken, 1817)
C. lythargyrella (Hübner, 1796)
Mesocrambus Blezysnski, 1957
M. candiellus (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)
Metacrambus Blezysnski, 1957
M. carectellus (Zeller, 1847)
Xanthocrambus Blezysnski, 1955
X. saxonellus (Zincken, 1820)
Chrysocrambus Blezysnski, 1957
C. linetellus (Fabricius, 1781)
cassentinellus (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)
C. craterellus (Scopoli, 1763)
Thisanotia Hübner, 1825
T. chrysonuchella (Scopoli, 1763)
culmella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Pediasia Hübner, 1825
P. fascelinella (Hübner, 1813)
P. jucundella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1847)
P. lutuella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
P. matricella (Treitschke, 1832)
P. aridella (Thunberg, 1788)
? ssp. *caradjaella* (Rebel, 1907)
P. kenderesiensis Fazekas, 1987
P. contaminella (Hübner, 1796)
Platytes Guenée, 1845
P. cerusella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
P. alpinella (Hübner, 1813)
Ancylolomia Hübner, 1825
? [*A. disparella* (Hübner, 1813)]^[17]
A. pectinatella (Zeller, 1847)
Talis Guenée, 1845

T. quercella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Schoenobiinae

Schoenobius Duponchel, 1836
Sch. gigantella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Donacaula Meyrick, 1890
D. forficella (Thunberg, 1794)
D. mucronella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Scirpophaga Treitschke, 1832
S. praelata (Scopoli, 1763)

Cybalomiinae

Hyperlais Marion, 1959
H. dulcinalis (Treitschke, 1835)

ACENTROPINAE ^[21]

Elophila Hübner, 1822
E. nymphaeata (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. rivulalis (Duponchel, 1834)
Acentria Stephens, 1829
A. ephemerella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Cataclysta Hübner, 1825
C. lemnata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Paraponyx Hübner, 1825
P. stratiotata (Linnaeus, 1758)
P. nivalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Nymphula Schrank, 1802
N. stagnata (Donovan, 1806)

ODONTIINAE

Hercynini
Metaxmeste Hübner, 1825
M. phrygialis (Hübner, 1796)

Odontiini

Aporodes Guenée, 1854
A. floralis (Hübner, 1809)
Cynaeda Hübner, 1825
C. dentalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
C. gigantea (Wocke, 1871)
Epascestria Hübner, 1825
E. pustulalis (Hübner, 1823)
Ephelis Lederer, 1863
? [*E. cruentalis* (Geyer, 1832)]^[20]
Atralata Sylván, 1947
A. albofascialis (Treitschke, 1829)
Titanio Hübner, 1825
T. normalis (Hübner, 1796)

Eurrhypini

Eurrhypis Hübner, 1825
E. polinalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

EVERGESTINAE

Evergestis Hübner, 1825
E. frumentalis (Linnaeus, 1761)

E. forficalis (Linnaeus, 1758)
E. extimalis (Scopoli, 1763)
E. limbata (Linnaeus, 1767)
E. pallidata (Hufnagel, 1767)
E. politalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
E. aenealis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Reskovitsia Szent-Ivány, 1942
R. alborivulalis (Eversmann, 1844)
Hellula Guenée, 1854
H. undalis (Fabricius, 1871)
PYRAUSTINAE
Pyraustini
Udea Guenée, 1845
U. ferrugalis (Hübner, 1796)
U. fulvalis (Hübner, 1809)
U. institalis (Hübner, 1819)
U. lutealis (Hübner, 1809)
U. prunalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
U. inquinatalis (Lienig & Zeller, 1846)
U. accolalis (Zeller, 1867)
U. olivalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Paracorsia Marion, 1959
P. repandalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Opsibotys Warren, 1890
O. fuscalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Loxostege Hübner, 1825
L. turbidalis (Treitschke, 1829)
L. deliblatica Szent-Ivány & Uhrík-Mészáros, 1942
L. aeruginalis (Hübner, 1796)
L. sticticalis (Linnaeus, 1761)
L. manualis (Geyer, 1832)
Achyra Guenée, 1849
A. nudalis (Hübner, 1796)
Ecpyrrhorhoe Hübner, 1825
E. rubiginalis (Hübner, 1796)
Harpadispis Agenjo, 1952
H. diffusalis (Guenée, 1854)
Meridiophila Marion, 1963
M. fascialis (Hübner, 1796)
Pyrausta Schrank, 1802
P. cingulata (Linnaeus, 1758)
P. rectefascialis Toll, 1936
P. virginalis Duponchel, 1832
P. sanguinalis (Linnaeus, 1767)
P. castalis Treitschke, 1829
P. despicata (Scopoli, 1763)
P. porphyralis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
P. aurata (Scopoli, 1763)
P. purpuralis (Linnaeus, 1758)
P. ostrinalis (Hübner, 1796)
P. falcatalis Guenée, 1854
P. obfuscata (Scopoli, 1763)
P. ledereri (Staudinger, 1870)
P. nigrata (Scopoli, 1763)
Uresiphita Hübner, 1825
U. gilvata (Fabricius, 1794)
Nascia Curtis, 1835
N. citalis (Hübner, 1796)
Sitochroa Hübner, 1825
S. palealis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
S. verticalis (Linnaeus, 1758)
Perinephela Hübner, 1825
P. lancealis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Phlyctaenia Hübner, 1825
Ph. coronata (Hufnagel, 1767)
Ph. stachydalis (Germar, 1821)
Ph. perlucidalis (Hübner, 1809)
Algedonia Lederer, 1863
A. luctualis (Hübner, 1793)
A. terrealis (Treitschke, 1829)
Sclerocona Meyrick, 1890
S. acutella (Eversmann, 1842)
Psammotis Hübner, 1825
P. pulveralis (Hübner, 1796)
Ostrinia Hübner, 1825
O. quadripunctalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
O. palustralis (Hübner, 1796)
O. nubilalis (Hübner, 1796)
Ebulea Doubleday, 1849
E. crocealis (Hübner, 1796)
E. testacealis (Zeller, 1847)
Anania Hübner, 1823
A. verbascalis ([Denis & Siffermüller], 1775)
A. funebris (Ström, 1768)
Eurrhyncha Hübner, 1825
E. hortulata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Paratalanta Meyrick, 1890
P. pandalis (Hübner, 1825)
P. hyalinalis (Hübner, 1796)
Spilomelini
Pleuroptya Meyrick, 1890
P. ruralis (Scopoli, 1763)
Mecyna Doubleday, 1849
M. flavalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
M. lutealis (Duponchel, 1833)
M. trinalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Agrotera Schrank, 1802
A. nemoralis (Scopoli, 1763)
Diasemia Hübner, 1825
D. reticularis (Linnaeus, 1761)
Palpita Hübner, 1808
P. unionalis (Hübner, 1796)
Amaurophanes Lederer, 1863
A. stigmosalis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)
Dolicharthria Stephens, 1834
D. punctalis ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)
Antigastra Lederer, 1863
A. catalaunalis (Duponchel, 1833)
Metasia Guenée, 1854
M. ophialis (Treitschke, 1829)
Nomophila Hübner, 1825
N. noctuella ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)

Bemerkungen

- [1] *Stigmella aeneofasciella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)]. Nach NIEUKERKEN (1996) aus Ungarn registriert. Seine Literaturdaten beruhen auf einer irrtümlichen Bestimmung, das Vorkommen in Ungarn ist nicht nachgewiesen.
- [2] *Xystophora lepidolampra* (Gozmány, 1952). Bisher nur aus Ungarn (Baja, Barcs, Budakeszi, Fonyód, Izsák, Kisbalaton, Ócsa) bekannt. Der taxonomische Status ist ungeklärt.
- [3] *Metzneria tristella* Rebel, 1901. Nur in einem einzelnen historischen Nachweis aus dem Budaer-Gebirge und Szada bekannt (GOZMÁNY 1958). Die Identität der Individuen aus Ungarn ist nicht sicher geklärt. Extrem lokale SW-europäische Art. Bisher nur aus Spanien und Frankreich registriert. Belegexemplare lagen mir nicht vor.
- [4] *Psamathocrita* ? sp. nach Elsner et al. 1999. Eine ungeklärte Art. In Ungarn bisher nur aus Csákberény (Vértes-Gebirge) und Hódmezővásárhely (Südungarn) gemeldet.
- [5] *Monochroa arundinetella* (Stainton, 1858). Nur in einem einzelnen historischen Nachweis bekannt (GOZMÁNY 1958). Nach Elsner et al. (1999) sind die Meldungen aus Ungarn bestätigungsbedürftig.
- [6] *Monochroa* ? sp. 1 nach Elsner et al. 1999. Eine ungeklärte Art aus Csákberény und SO Slowakei.
- [7] *Monochroa* ? sp. 3 nach Elsner et al. 1999. Eine ungeklärte Art aus Nyíregyháza (Ostungarn).
- [8] *Bryotropha* ? sp. nach Elsner & Karsholt, 1999. Eine ungeklärte Art aus Jósvalfő (HG), Vevéce (CZ) und Slovensky Raj (SK). In der Vergangenheit mit den nahe verwandten Arten *Bryotropha desertella* (Douglas, 1850) und *B. terrella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775) verwechselt (?).
- [9] *Bryotropha dryadella* (Zeller, 1850). In Ungarn bisher nur aus Sandgebieten gemeldet (GOZMÁNY 1958). Nach ELSNER et al. (1999) betreffen sämtliche Meldungen aus Ungarn andere *Bryotropha*-Arten. Aus Mittel-Europa noch nicht gemeldet. Südliche Art.
- [10] *Sophronia marginella* Toll, 1936. Nach ELSNER et al. (1999) ist der taxonomische Status ungeklärt. Alle von uns untersuchten Exemplare weisen keine brauchbaren Unterscheidungsmerkmale gegenüber *Sophronia consanguinella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1854 auf.
- [11] *Syncopacma azosterella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854). Der taxonomische Status ist ungeklärt. Nach ELSNER et al. (1999) steht diese Art *Syncopacma suecicella* (Wolf, 1958) sehr nahe. *S. azosterella* wird von uns als Nomen dubium angesehen, da kein Typenmaterial mehr vorhanden zu sein scheint.
- [12] *Syncopacma albipalpella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854). In Ungarn bisher nur aus Kaposvár gemeldet (GOZMÁNY 1958). Nach Elsner et al. (1999) für Ungarn noch nicht registriert.
- [13] *Neophaculata ericetella* (Geyer, 1832). In Ungarn bisher nur aus Uzsza gemeldet (GOZMÁNY 1958). Nach ELSNER et al. (1999) boreomontane Art und in Ungarn fehlend.
- [14] *Platyptilia calodactyla* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775)]. Nur in einem einzelnen historischen Nachweis aus Ungarn bekannt (ABAFI-AIGNER et al. 1896). Nach FAZEKAS (1996) beziehen sich diese Daten auf das Gebiet der heutigen Slowakei und Rumäniens. Ein Exemplar aus Ungarn lag bisher nicht vor.
- [15] *Crambus perlella* (Scopoli, 1763). Nach FAZEKAS (1993) ist ssp. monochromellus Herrich-Schäffer, 1854 eine in den Alpen lebende Unterart. Nach neueren Untersuchungen kommt sie in Ungarn nicht vor.
- [16] *Catoptria falsella* ([Denis & Schiff.], 1775). *Catoptria persephone* Bleszynski, 1956 **syn. n.**: Die Genitalien sind mit *falsella* identisch.
- [17] *Ancylolomia disparella* (Hübner, 1813) Nach ABAFI-AIGNER et al. (1896) wurde die Art in Sopron (W-Ungarn) gefunden. Der Verbleib des Belegexemplars ist unbekannt.
- [18] *Zophodia grossulariella* (Hübner, 1809). Nur in einem einzelnen historischen Nachweis aus Ungarn bekannt (ABAFI-AIGNER et al. 1896). Die Art ist in Ungarn nicht sicher nachgewiesen.
- [19] *Hypochalcia griseoaenella* (Ragonot, 1887) Nur in einem einzigem historischen Nachweis aus Ungarn bekannt (Rebel 1901). Die Art ist in Ungarn nicht sicher nachgewiesen.
- [20] *Ephelis cruentalis* (Geyer, 1832). Bisher nur aus Budapest bekannt (SZABÓKY 1981). Der Ursprung des Exemplars ist unsicher. Der Autor vermutete, dass es mit dem Reisegepäck von einer Auslandssammelreise eingeschleppt wurde.
- [21] ACENTROPINAE Stephens, 1835: SOLIS (1999, Bull. zool. Nom. 56: 31–33) hat bei der Internationalen Nomenklatur-Kommission (ICZN) den Antrag gestellt, dem Namen Nymphulinae Vorrang vor Acentropinae zu gewähren. Nach SPEIDEL & MEY (2000: Bull. Zool. Nom 56: 46–48) sollte der prioritätsberechtigige Name Acentropinae Verwendung finden. Eine diesbezügliche Entscheidung der ICZN steht noch aus und daher wird hier einstweilen der prioritätsberechtigige Name verwendet.

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